

TIME4CS

SUPPORTING SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTIONAL CHANGES TO
PROMOTE CITIZEN SCIENCE IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

D5.3: Final Evaluation and Impact Assessment Report

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Abbreviations

APRE – Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
AU – Aarhus University
CC-CS – Competence Center - Citizen Science
CHX – Crowdhelix Limited
CRG – Fundacio Centre De Regulacio Genomica
CS - Citizen Science
DoA – Description of Action
EC - European Commission
ECSA - European Citizen Science Association
EPA - Environmental Protection Agency
ESE - Engagement & Public Education
ESF – Fondation Européenne De La Science
SFI - Science Foundation Ireland
GA – Grounding Actions
IAs - Intervention Areas
IPIC - SFI Centre for photonics, is Ireland’s centre of excellence for research, innovation and PhD training in photonics – the science and application of light
IRC - Irish Research Council
IUA - Irish University Association
KPI - Key Performance Indicator
KTU – Kaunas University of Technology
MQP - Management and Quality Plan
PI - Principal Investigator
RRI - Research & Innovation

SDG -Sustainable Development Goals
SFI - Science Foundation Ireland
RFOs - Research Funding organisations
RPOs - Research Performing organisations
T-UCC – Tyndall National Institute University College Cork
UCL – University College London
UniSR – Università Vita-Salute San Raffaele
UZH - Citizen Science Center Zurich
WP - Work Package
Y2 - Project Year 2
ZSI – Zentrum Für Soziale Innovation Gmbh

Executive Summary

The current document, titled “Final Evaluation and Impact Assessment Report”, has been developed within the framework of the TIME4CS project which is funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101006201.

Evaluation and impact assessment activities in TIME4CS aim to:

- jointly assess the progress of implemented institutional changes in the participating organisations and understand mutual learning effects between Front-Runners and Implementers of the project.
- provide research performing organisations (RPOs) and research funding organisations (RFOs) with a monitoring toolkit to self-assess and monitor their progress towards organisational change (see D5.4 Monitoring Toolkit for RFOs and RPOs¹).
- learn about the implementation process of institutional changes in implementing organisations to understand the different pathways taken within the organisations and their intended and unintended consequences.

In TIME4CS, evaluation was integrated in all project activities from the very beginning - in a first step we elaborated an Evaluation and Impact Assessment plan (D5.1: Evaluation and Impact Assessment Plan²) together with representatives from the four implementing organisations - CRG, KTU, UniSR and Tyndall (which we call Implementers in this deliverable). This plan defined key indicators for the summative and formative evaluation, as well as evaluation instruments and a timeline. Also, a stock-taking exercise with the Implementers helped to understand the baseline before implementing the Roadmaps and Grounding Actions. Based on the initial planning and an interim stock taking, we elaborated an Interim Impact Assessment report in year 2 (D5.2 Interim Evaluation and Impact Assessment Report³). The main insight was the fact that the Implementers faced several challenges related to the integration of Citizen Science in their research activities. Nonetheless, Implementers had succeeded in triggering first institutional changes to support Citizen Science. In every implementer organisation “core teams” with representatives of different research support services had started to form, plan and continually adapt the Grounding Actions to the given circumstances.

The last year of the project was dedicated to further implementing institutional changes and analysing their effect on individual participants as well as at an institutional level. Data collection for the evaluation and impact assessment was intensified at the end of the project with workshops and expert interviews organised for each implementer in October and November 2023. The outcomes of these evaluation activities, together with an update of the stock-taking exercise and the evaluation matrix, showed the considerable changes that the project had triggered within the involved RPOs.

We learned that actively engaging citizens in research was perceived by many researchers across the Implementers as an “on-top” activity in their already very competitive work environment, which additionally required specific skills on ethics, data quality, citizens’ engagement and facilitation, etc. For some research

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10405577>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5805863>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7486206>

topics, the implementation of the Citizen Science methodology was not self-evident (sometimes perceived as not possible) and required careful consideration, such as the engagement of citizens when working with very expensive laboratory equipment or in sensible fields like biomedicine. We noted that many researchers have difficulties in distinguishing Citizen Science from science communication and other forms of participatory research like patient engagement. Operating in an environment with very scarce resources with regard to time and budget, it was perceived as a challenge for many scientists to engage in this new research approach, especially because the advantage of this involvement for their research was not clear to them. The main reservations encountered were related to the additional time and efforts required for citizen engagement, concerns about data quality, or simply the fact that it was not clear how citizens could generally contribute to fundamental research in their domains of health and ICT. Given these challenges, the first activities of the TIME4CS team members in the different implementer organisations were dedicated to contextual exploration and the building of Citizen Science “core teams”. These were made of representatives from different support services like Open Science Offices, Science Communication teams and Training departments. The teams started to develop an in-depth understanding of the different shapes that Citizen Science activities can take and how these best link to the research focus and context of doing research in the different RPOs. In the 3-years project runtime, the core teams reached out to the international Citizen Science community, started to engage in European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) working groups, realizing that networking and learning from other more experienced organisations is crucial. In this regard, the mutual exchange with the Front-Runners of the TIME4CS project was key and the “mentoring visits” organised in spring 2023 were perceived as “eye opening” and “turning point” events for all of the Implementers (see D3.5: Report on TIME4CS Mentoring Programme⁴). The core teams developed targeted approaches of explaining and demonstrating the value of Citizen Science to researchers and the management, mainly by:

- elaborating guidelines on Citizen Science for their organisations and collecting material and resources which were shared on the inter- and intranets of the RPOs,
- developing course content on Citizen Science for Master- and PhD-students and Postdocs,
- offering short, practical workshops that were adapted to the specific research context, inviting external speakers and role models to show more experienced researchers how Citizen Science can concretely benefit their research,
- and investigating which support structures within their organisations were needed to lower the entry barrier of researchers to the Citizen Science research approach.

The creation of internal contact points for Citizen Science as well as first discussions on the adaptation of researchers’ evaluation criteria were main outcomes of the structural changes and really key to raise motivation of researchers to engage with this approach.

The core teams also succeeded in reaching out to researchers who can act as ambassadors for Citizen Science amongst their colleagues. As a result of these efforts, we see in all four Implementers concrete ideas and plans on how to set up first Citizen Science initiatives as part of existing research evolving. Some of them are even in the realisation stage or submitted as proposals to funding agencies.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8082479>

All these structural changes and impact on individual participants and at organisational level show that TIME4CS successfully started to trigger institutional change within the RPOs that will be sustained also after the end of the project.

The main lessons learned on how to implement these changes are an important source of information for other RPOs which want to support Citizen Science within their institutions. They will be able to use the self-assessment and reflection tools stemming from TIME4CS (D5.4 Monitoring Toolkit for RFOs and RPOs⁵) as valuable resources in their journey towards institutional change.

The most important recommendations from the implementation process include the creation of core teams, the implementation of training, the motivation of researchers and the planning of activities. They can be found in Chapter 8 of this document and are illustrated in the following Figure 1.

Figure 1: Recommendations on how to trigger institutional change

Front-Runners equally benefited from their involvement in the TIME4CS activities, getting a clearer picture of the activities they, themselves organise within their institutions and developing strategies on how to better communicate these activities to their audiences. They learned about all the challenges that Implementers face when driving Citizen Science top-down in RPOs and how the different contexts influence the paths and activities that need to be taken for change to happen. As a result, they started thinking about their own new

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10405577>

Grounding Actions and realised that despite different levels of institutional support for Citizen Science, the challenges remain the same in all organisations: a sustainable institutional funding for internal support structures and a wide-spread knowledge on Citizen Science amongst researchers and support staff is crucial to making Citizen Science an integral and widely applied research method.

1. Introduction

This document presents interim evaluation and impact assessment activities and outcomes and is structured along the following main chapters:

2. About the project

Provides a short introduction about the project and the applied methodology.

3. Indicators and Instruments used for the final impact evaluation of Institutional Change

Gives an overview of the indicators of institutional change defined in the TIME4CS project and the evaluation instruments applied in the project.

4. - 7. Institutional Changes in CRG, KTU, Tyndall, UniSR

These chapters present the core of the deliverable. They start with a short introduction of each Implementer and their baseline situation regarding institutional changes at the beginning of the project. Then the main institutional changes are introduced, and the outputs and outcomes of the Grounding Actions presented.

8. Main lessons learned about the implementation process

Provides a rich source of information for other RPOs who wish to trigger institutional changes to support Citizen Science within their organisations.

9. Main lessons learned of Front-Runners

Summarizing the main findings and lessons learned of the participating Front-Runner organisations, who equally benefited from the participation in the project and the mutual exchange.

10. Monitoring of project KPIs

Presents the main KPIs related to the project objectives.

11. Conclusions

3. About the project

TIME4CS aims at supporting and facilitating the implementation of sustainable Institutional Changes in Research Performing organisations (RPOs) to promote Citizen Science and public engagement (citizens and citizens associations) in science and technology.

Public engagement - in all its forms and applications, including Citizen Science - has a strong structural, transformative power at various levels of research and innovation processes. It incorporates a variety of viewpoints into problem formulation and research questions whilst considering moral or ethical societal concerns.

TIME4CS aims at facilitating a way in which the scientific ecosystem could better take societal views into consideration by supporting RPOs- i.e., research entities such as universities and research centres - in defining and implementing institutional changes that can lead to a better and more effective engagement of citizens in research and innovation. Those institutional changes inside RPOs will entail a transformation of their governance systems by considering both the social - mindset of people inside the organisation – and the organisational - norms, protocols, procedures, policy - aspects of RPOs. To facilitate this process, TIME4CS has identified 4 Intervention Areas that alone or combined can stimulate the institutional changes necessary to promote public engagement in R&I activities:

1. Research
2. Education & Awareness
3. Support Resources & Infrastructure
4. Policy & Assessment.

For each Intervention Area, a set of Grounding Actions (GA) was defined. The Grounding Actions are to be considered as seeds to be sown, paving the way to Institutional Changes within RPOs. TIME4CS builds on the close collaboration between Front-Runners - RPOs with a comprehensive expertise in Citizen Science and that have already undergone institutional changes - and Implementers - beneficiaries still in the early stage of the institutional adoption and/or maintenance of Citizen Science in their organisations.

The specific objectives of the project are:

- To increase knowledge on the actions leading to Institutional Changes in RPOs necessary to promote Public Engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology
- To support TIME4CS RPOs in the implementation of actions leading to Institutional Changes through continuous mutual learning and knowledge transfer programme
- To build a dynamic and inclusive Citizen Science stakeholder community
- To increase the awareness of the need for a sustainable and flexible organisation of RPOs' governance system to better respond to the evolving relationship between science and society.

To ensure a sustainable change towards public engagement in scientific processes, TIME4CS' work plan is structured in 7 interlinked Work Packages covering all stages of the institutional adoption of Citizen Science. A comprehensive analysis of the institutional adoption and maintenance of Citizen Science capacity from the literature and a systematic mapping of the knowledge provided by Front-Runners in relation to the 4 Intervention Areas, fed the definition of tailored Roadmaps for Implementers, detailing specific Grounding Actions that would be carried out during the project. TIME4CS has established a knowledge transfer and mutual learning programme between Front-Runners and Implementers. Moreover, TIME4CS built capacity to enable institutional and cultural changes needed for Citizen Science adoption. Training activities were developed to contribute to raising awareness and creating a community around TIME4CS, as they were not exclusive to TIME4CS beneficiaries but open to the whole Citizen Science community. The whole process was constantly monitored and assessed in work package 5, which is responsible for this document, through the

development of a set of indicators to assess Institutional Change to promote citizens' engagement in science along the four Intervention Areas defined by TIME4CS.

Evaluation and impact assessment comprised of:

- a summative evaluation of the project's benefits in participating organisations
- a formative evaluation of the implementation of roadmaps and Grounding Actions that helps to iteratively shape the Grounding Actions, the training formats, encounters and materials developed by the project

4. Indicators and Instruments used for the final impact evaluation of Institutional Change

Evaluation and impact assessment activities in TIME4CS aimed at jointly assessing the progress of implemented institutional changes in the participating organisations and understanding mutual learning effects between Front-Runners and Implementers of the project. With this aim we have developed a set of indicators for institutional change that were assessed at three strategic points throughout the runtime of the project. For each implementer, a logic model of Grounding Actions and expected/realised outputs and outcomes was created and updated in year 2 and 3 of the project. We organised evaluation workshops with each Implementer at the end of year 3 to discuss the impact of the project and did additional 2-3 interviews with representatives of the 4 RPOs. All these instruments are described in more detail in the following chapter and visualised on the following timeline (Figure 2).

3.1. Stock-taking of Indicators for Institutional Change

In TIME4CS we believe that **both the bottom-up institutional changes - driven by the modification of social patterns shared by the people within an organisation - and top-down approaches** - driven by changes in organisational structures - are needed for a sustainable embedding of Citizen Science.

Thus, evaluation focused on both aspects:

- **Changes at an institutional level:** These are structured along the four intervention areas “Education & Awareness”, “Support Resources & Infrastructures”, “Policy & Assessment”, “Research” and are presented in the upper four rectangles in Figure 3. The indicators for changes at an institutional level are aligned with the set of indicators developed in WP1 for the case study analysis. This alignment allows to reflect and present the TIME4CS Implementers according to the same framework as the other 30 international cases selected in WP1⁶.
- **Changes at an individual level:** These changes noted within researchers, students and support staff are presented in the bottom rectangle of Figure 3. They cannot be attributed to one specific intervention area only. For instance: Increases in knowledge and skills of individual participants are an expected outcome of institutional changes related to “Education & Awareness”; but can also be triggered by the implementation of a general contact point for Citizen Science, thus being related to “Support Resources & Infrastructures”. And attributes of individuals, like knowledge, motivation and interest, might not only be a consequence of institutional changes but also a pre-condition to drive institutional change.

An overview of indicators in the four intervention areas can be seen in Figure 3.

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807507>

Indicators for Institutional Changes to support citizen science in RPOs

Figure 3: Indicators for institutional change in RPOs. Top four boxes are institutional level changes, bottom grey box contains individual level changes.

To assess institutional changes in implementer organisations, WP5 conducted a first “stock-taking” exercise with the four Implementers at the beginning of the project. For the interim evaluation report, we conducted a second stock-taking exercise at the end of project year 2 and compared the results with the initial stock-taking exercise. For this final impact assessment report, a third stock-taking exercise was organised at the end of project year 3.

3.2. Evaluation models of outputs and outcomes

The collection of institutional changes which relate to the four intervention areas and are closely connected to the work done in WP1, were amended by a fine-tuned and detailed discussion of expected outputs and outcomes for each grounding action in the different implementer organisations.

Inspired by the Logic Framework Approach (LFA), a structured process was applied to understand the consequences of the activities planned in each of the Implementers to achieve the intended institutional change. We created a logic model (Table 1) for each Implementer that showed: the planned Grounding Actions, involved stakeholders, expected/realized outputs and outcomes, potential indicators to measure outputs and outcomes, data collection instruments, and individual stakeholder representatives who we could involve in data collection.

Table 1: Implementers' logic model template

Grounding action	Involved stakeholders	Outputs and outcomes	Measures	Means of data gathering	Individual stakeholders

This template was used to guide the review, discussion, and explication of all applicable components within the individual Implementers. The template was initially filled by the ZSI evaluation team with content based on the D2.1⁷ and then collaboratively discussed and amended with the implementer organisations at the end of year 2 and year 3. Thus the logic models presented in this deliverable show the outputs and outcomes of TIME4CS Grounding Actions at the end of year 3.

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5743298>

3.3. Evaluation and impact assessment workshops and interviews

The final evaluation and impact assessment workshops were organised at the end of the 3rd project year with representatives from the core teams of each implementer organisation.

In these interactive online sessions, the WP5 team guided Implementers through a set of collaborative reflection exercises to:

- Work on a timeline and reflect on all the TIME4CS activities in the implementer organisation since the beginning of the project
- Discuss problems and solutions encountered during these activities
- Define the main outcomes and
- Reflect on the impact of TIME4CS on management, researchers, students and support staff

The collaborative working space for the workshops was Miro. An example of the Miro board used is presented in Figure 4:

Figure 4: Working environment of the Final evaluation workshop

The discussions during the workshops were audio-recorded and served the evaluation team as an important source of information to identify project outcomes and impacts, but also main lessons learned from the implementation process.

In addition, twelve expert interviews with people outside the core teams were organised to capture the opinions of those who were only partly involved in the TIME4CS activities. These were:

- 2 interviews with KTU representatives (head of project office and head of library),

- 3 interviews with Tyndall representatives (head of Tyndall group, UCC (University of Cork) community officer, Tyndall head of graduate studies and EPE (Education and Public Engagement)),
- 3 interviews with CRG representatives (director of CRG, newly appointed Citizen Science contact point, bioinformatic researcher)
- 4 interviews with UniSR representatives (3 researchers, 1 nurse)

In the next four chapters we will take a closer look at Implementer organisations CRG, KTU, UniSR and Tyndall. We will start each chapter with a short introduction to the Implementer, especially the situation encountered when starting the Grounding Actions. Then we will introduce a summary of the main outcomes of the TIME4CS project - in relation to the baseline that we encountered at the beginning of the project. We continue with a more detailed description of the four intervention areas and their status at the end of the TIME4CC project and conclude each chapter with the Implementers' evaluation matrix - showing the outputs and outcomes of the different Grounding Actions.

5. Institutional Changes in CRG

4.1. Summary of TIME4CS outcomes in CRG (Barcelona, Spain)

The Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG) is an international biomedical research institute of excellence, created in December 2000. The CRG is a highly competitive research centre, with a very high rotation system of scientists (PhD students and postdoctoral researchers can stay a maximum of 5 years at CRG and junior principal investigators (PIs) 9 years).

Main barriers for Citizen Science encountered at the beginning of the project: The perception of Citizen Science by researchers and the disciplinary challenges

Citizen science requires time and dedication and does not always guarantee the production of publishable results in the medium term. This is very challenging for PhDs, postdocs or junior PIs who need to publish in a relatively short time to advance their career when they leave the CRG. In addition, since CRG has a focus mostly on fundamental science, involving expensive and highly sophisticated technologies, the application of the Citizen Science methodology is not immediate and requires considering very carefully how to involve citizens in some of the CRG research projects.

Another barrier is the lack of knowledge or understanding of the Citizen Science methodology by researchers. After leading two Citizen Science projects at the institute, researchers are still confused about Citizen Science principles. They identify Citizen Science with some aspects of public engagement and do not realise that Citizen Science is a different methodology to conduct real research projects. They perceive that they need to spend much more time in aspects which are not necessary in a traditional research project. Finally, some scientists are sceptical of involving non-specialised people in their projects and worry about the quality of their research.

Institutional support for Citizen Science at the beginning of the project

When CRG started the TIME4CS project, they had two successful Citizen Science projects⁸ and some selected researchers who had experience in Citizen Science. Despite the two successful Citizen Science projects, Citizen Science was not a commonly used approach due to the complexity of linking biomedical research to Citizen Science activities. CRG had a Citizen Science facilitator who was financed by the two projects and supported other researchers in writing proposals and engaging citizens in research. The facilitator had established connections to ECSA and national Citizen Science actors in Spain, but still no sustainable funding for this position was in place. Thus, the Citizen Science facilitator had to leave the CRG in the first TIME4CS project year, consequently neither a dedicated person, nor resources in terms of knowledge, material, etc. were available to support Citizen Science. In this situation, it was a key objective for CRG to create a clearer understanding amongst researchers on how Citizen Science can be of use in their specific context, have a more sustainable approach for funding a Citizen Science facilitator and create the institutional guidelines and policies to support Citizen Science projects to take shape. The situation at the project start is depicted in Figure 5.

CRG: Institutional Support - Starting situation

Figure 5: CRG Institutional Support - Starting Situation

⁸ GENIGMA was an experiment within the EU project [ORION Open Science](#). It was a co-created mobile game app to obtain the map of the breast cancer genome, it was launched in January 2022 and closed in October 2022. [Here](#) is a summary of the challenge, the players and the results obtained.

[SACA LA LENGUA](#) (Stick out your tongue) was a Citizen Science project on the mouth microbiome with a high national impact that lasted 4 years (2 runs). Currently the project has been completed and the scientific results are being published. There is also a summary page of the project in English [here](#).

Institutional support for Citizen Science at the end of the project

After implementing the Grounding Actions in CRG for three years, we can see that TIME4CS has set the basis to support Citizen Science in a more formal manner.

New structures were built internally to allow for Citizen Science to sustain and further develop after the end of the project:

- **A strong Citizen Science core team** with representatives of the Communication team, the Strategy and Funding department and the Training and Academic Office driving the actions for institutional changes.
- **New pathways for Citizen Science, starting small:** The conversations of this core team with the Front-Runners during the mentoring visit resulted in a deeper understanding of different types of Citizen Science. They realised to better start with smaller Citizen Science initiatives as part of their traditional research. It was important for them to collect positive experiences that apply the Citizen Science methodology in smaller initiatives, resulting in more recognition from researchers step-by-step.
- **Workshops and training:** A few PIs attended the workshops of the training visit. The workshops were a huge success and not only resulted in having first Citizen Science ambassadors outside of the Citizen Science core team, but also helped design two new proposals for Citizen Science projects that were submitted in 2023.
- **Citizen science info hub:** The co-created Citizen Science section on the internet as well as guidelines for implementing Citizen Science in CRG are an important source of information for researchers.
- **Courses:** There is a session on Citizen Science integrated in the courses and curriculum of PhD students and this session is also made available to the whole CRG community.
- **The Citizen Science contact point** is nominated. She is a project manager with a focus on impact who also promotes Citizen Science as a research methodology and helps to design the projects accordingly. She will also keep the website and other material up to date. The funding for Citizen Science facilitators that actively support the implementation of Citizen Science projects will be included in project proposals.
- **Open Science:** Citizen science is integrated in the Open Science Institutional framework, which is very important for the integration in institutional structures.
- **The developed Citizen Science policy** is on hold and will be rolled out if more need for regulation is seen.
- **Awareness-raising:** All the activities raised awareness, knowledge and interest in the Citizen Science approach especially among support services and project managers. They learned why this approach is important for CRG and how they can apply it.
- **A team** of ambassadors (from management, support services, but also first researchers) will sustain future activities.

Figure 6 presents an overview of Institutional Support for Citizen Science in CRG at the end of the project.

CRG: Institutional Support at the end of the project

Time4CS set the basis to support citizen science in a more formal manner, there were new structures built internally to allow for citizen science to sustain and further develop (e.g. the CS contact point, the CS section, the guidelines). Time4CS helped to raise awareness and interest and get first multipliers to sustain the activities (from management, support services, but also first researchers).

Figure 6: CRG Institutional Support - End Situation

Future activities to support Citizen Science in CRG:

- Citizen science and active engagement of citizens in research will be integrated in researchers' evaluation schemes
- The core team is exploring the opportunities to offer seed funding for Citizen Science to researchers
- If the two proposals with a Citizen Science dimension are accepted, they will serve to intensify communication about and capacity building for Citizen Science within CRG
- Regular internal networking meetings with external experts are planned as important triggers and role models for researchers.

4.2. Stock taking of institutional changes at the end of year 3

The previous 2 sections have provided a summary of the main TIME4CS achievements in CRG. In this section we will describe the activities under the four intervention areas in more detail.

Intervention Area “Research”

At the end of the TIME4CS project, there are no new Citizen Science projects running at the CRG, but, recently, **two project proposals have incorporated Citizen Science elements to their research methodologies**, in part thanks to the collaboration of the new Citizen Science Contact Point and a scientific project manager. This is a result of the increased awareness about the Citizen Science methodology of the research support teams, a consequence of the institutionalization of Citizen Science and the Grounding Actions 1, 2 and 5.

Already from the beginning of the TIME4CS project, CRG is a member of the ECSA and a member of the Barcelona Citizen Science Office promoted by the Barcelona City Council. They have collaborated on several occasions with the [Ibercivis](#) Foundation, which brings Citizen Science together at a Spanish level. So has the former Citizen Science facilitator of CRG participated as an expert in the Citizen Science encounters organised by the Ibercivis Foundation, to define a national strategy on Citizen Science. She also participated in Citizen Science related workshops and conferences of the ECSA. Since the Citizen Science facilitator left CRG in September 2022, there are no representatives of CRG actively engaged in these networking organisations, although the Citizen Science Contact Point is getting familiar and learning about the methodology, and, with time, would be more actively involved in networking events.

On the other hand, a Citizen Science webpage has been created under the Open Science section with information about the methodology, about the Citizen Science Contact Point, about the support offered by the CRG and gathering useful resources such as the guidelines developed under the TIME4CS project (GA3).

Intervention Area “Education & Awareness”

There is still very limited knowledge about Citizen Science among CRG researchers, since the number of scientists attending the Citizen Science training workshops delivered during this year was low. However, the **scientists that attended** are very interested in developing Citizen Science projects, which may have a **multiplier effect** in spreading the word amongst their colleagues. At the other end of the spectrum, the majority of the **scientific project managers and grants specialists attended the training workshops**, which has had a significant impact on their awareness, Citizen Science knowledge and their role in suggesting the methodology to scientists in project proposals.

In addition to the training workshops, for the second consecutive year a Citizen Science session has been delivered during the PhD Course, addressed to new PhDs, and has been recorded and added to the moodle in which CRG trainings are gathered. This talk has also been disseminated to the whole CRG and is available on the CRG Citizen Science website. Although it is difficult to know the impact of these sessions for PhDs, their aim was to inform the new PhDs about the existence of a research methodology that includes public participation and that has a lot of benefits, since Citizen Science is unknown for most of them. Basically, the talks plant a seed for the future, since new PhDs are at a too early stage of their careers to develop a Citizen Science project, but also that they would spread the message amongst other colleagues and lab members. The significant implementation derived from the TIME4CS project is that these sessions have been

implemented as part of the institutional PhD Course, which is mandatory for all new PhDs, and will happen every year (GA6).

For the post-project (2024-2026) and the stabilisation (2027-2028) periods, it is planned to organise a scientific talk given by an internationally renowned scientist who has applied Citizen Science to a biomedical research project (this action was considered in the first version of the Roadmap but it couldn't be implemented). Also, it is planned to organise periodical informative sessions for CRG researchers (and, maybe, for researchers from other institutions) to contribute to spread the awareness of the methodology, help design Citizen Science projects and foster collaborations.

Intervention Area “Support Resources & Infrastructures”

Since 2014, when Saca La Lengua started, till the end of September 2022, when Genigma ended, there was a Citizen Science facilitator hired to support and guide the CRG Citizen Science projects. Since the position was not structural and depended on external funding of specific Citizen Science projects, at the moment there is no Citizen Science facilitator at the CRG as there are no Citizen Science projects running.

Since the previous experience with Citizen Science projects has shown the CRG that having a person dedicated to promoting this methodology is a need, the appointment of a Citizen Science Contact Point was added as a new Grounding Action to the second version of the Roadmap (GA5) and has been already implemented. This person is the cornerstone for the development and implementation of Citizen Science projects at the CRG, so will highly contribute to the sustainability of the project. The Contact Point will also contribute to looking for partners and for funding opportunities.

To help researchers and the Citizen Science Contact Point to design and develop Citizen Science projects, guidelines for internal use have been already developed (GA3) and disseminated to all the CRG community. Guidelines are available at the CRG Intranet together with the rest of the internal guidelines and are linked from the CRG Citizen Science webpage.

Regarding funding, there is no internal funding for Citizen Science in CRG now. Since funding for Citizen Science projects is an important challenge, the CRG thus plans to include this cost in project proposal budgets when applying to funding calls, since there is no internal budget for this. Additionally, it is foreseen to allocate an internal budget for funding a Citizen Science project, which will be selected through an internal open call, during the stabilisation period of the project (GA11 -Final Roadmap).

Intervention Area “Policy & Assessment”

Science communication and public outreach is an integral part of the Strategic Plan 2021-2024 of CRG. CRG has a Policy on Open Access to publications and a Policy on Research Data Management.

Since there was no policy regarding Citizen Science before TIME4CS, GA4 was dedicated to elaborating a Citizen Science Policy to have clear guidelines about critical points of a Citizen Science project. After the document was drafted, and after the Mentoring Visit with the Front-Runners, it was decided not to publish

it because the CRG is not at a stage of needing a policy on Citizen Science. It was agreed that having a policy could present more obstacles than benefits for researchers at this moment, so the draft is saved, and the Citizen Science Contact Point will implement it when it is needed. The document describes good practices for a Citizen Science project in terms of the roles of every party, quality of data, ethical aspects, authorship, etc. It also describes the support and resources available at the CRG for Citizen Science projects.

The CRG director supports Citizen Science and has been promoting the two first CRG Citizen Science projects in different forums. The researchers are not explicitly encouraged to pursue Citizen Science activities, but participation in public engagement is positively appreciated.

As part of the TIME4CS Grounding Actions (GA8), the CRG plans to incorporate the recognition of Citizen Science (societal) impact in the internal evaluation processes.

CRG members are expected to be familiar and comply with the Barcelona Biomedical Research Park Code of Good Scientific Practice⁹, which defines and strictly bans scientific misconduct. CRG researchers are also bound by the CERCA Code of Conduct¹⁰ (CERCA being the public institution that supervises and supports all research institutes created by the Government of Catalonia). Every new researcher at CRG must undertake an online certified course about research integrity.

4.3. Overview of GAs, outputs and outcomes

In this section we take a closer look at the Grounding Actions, their outcomes and impacts at the end of the TIME4CS project.

⁹ <https://share.prbb.org/public.php?service=files&t=2ce671a9a38e27574bbe52b9c5745188&download>

¹⁰ https://cerca.cat/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/Codi-de-conducta-CERCA_nov2018.pdf

Table 2: Evaluation model of CRG

Grounding actions	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
1. Planning changes in organisational structures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To include Citizen Science as a pillar in the CRG Open Science framework. To create and publish the content for the Citizen Science section at the CRG Open Science web page. To disseminate the new structural place of Citizen Science to all the CRG community. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication team, Strategy and Funding team Citizen Science Contact Point Higher management 	Output: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 co-creation workshops organised 5 employees involved in the co-creation of the content Content of the Citizen Science section created and published Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased recognition and knowledge of Citizen Science amongst the Communication team, the Strategy and Funding team, the Citizen Science Contact Point and the rest of the CRG admin community and scientists
2. Raising internal awareness & training researchers on Citizen Science & Including Citizen Science sessions in the PhD Course and other relevant training networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To organise an online talk describing success stories of other Citizen Science projects, explained by researchers with previous experience in running Citizen Science projects. To set up Citizen Science training programmes for PhD students and include them in the mandatory training courses for this community To set up Citizen Science training programmes for post-docs and Admin & PIs Mapping the appropriate training networks in which include a session about Citizen Science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication team Training and Academic Office Internal and external Citizen Science experts PhD students, Post-doc , PIs, Relevant admin staff 	Output: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 external research for an inspirational talk identified and contacted, but finally it was not possible to invite the speaker 45 PhD students introduced to Citizen Science (2 different talks in 2 editions of the PhD Course in 2022 and 2023). Session included as part of the core content of the annual course (GA6) 1 registered talk from the second edition of the session at the PhD course uploaded to the CRG moodle and disseminated and available to all the CRG 2 training workshops for the Strategy and Funding team and researchers delivered The map of training networks is being developed Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased knowledge and awareness about Citizen Science in the training team, the 45 PhD students, the 15 members of the admin team (4 persons were not from the CRG), the 4 scientists that attended the training workshops and the people who have watched the talk. All these persons might have talked to their colleagues

		about Citizen Science, although this is unknown
3. Developing institutional guidelines on the implementation of Citizen Science projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To develop institutional guidelines on the principles of Citizen Science and how to design and run a Citizen Science project. To publish and disseminate the guidelines through CRG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication team Strategy and Funding team Citizen Science Contact Point 	Output: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 co-creation workshops organised 5 employees involved in the co-creation of the guidelines Content for guidelines created, published in the CRG Intranet and disseminated to the CRG community Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased knowledge and awareness about Citizen Science in the engaged actors and in the rest of the CRG community
4. Developing an institutional policy about Citizen Science projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To develop an institutional policy for Citizen Science at the CRG To publish and disseminate the policy for Citizen Science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communications team Legal team Strategy & Funding team Higher management 	Output: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 co-creation workshop organised 5 employees involved in the creation of the institutional policy Draft for the institutional policy about Citizen Science created. The policy will not be published and put into force until is the moment Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased knowledge and awareness about Citizen Science amongst the engaged actors Awareness about the obstacles that a Citizen Science policy may pose and the need to wait until the Citizen Science scenario requires it so that having a policy is beneficial and not detrimental for Citizen Science projects
5: Appointing a Citizen Science Contact Point <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussing with the internal stakeholders involved the most appropriate person/team to be appointed as the Citizen Science contact point and decide their tasks and responsibilities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizen Science Contact Point Strategy and Funding team Communications team 	Output: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Appointed a member of the Strategy and Funding team as a Citizen Science Contact Point Contact Point informed about Citizen Science, the TIME4CS project and the current situation of the Grounding Actions at the CRG Contact Point involved in some of the Grounding Actions and the definition of the Final Roadmap

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communicating the decision to the person/team and agree on their role. ● Communicating this new role to the CRG community. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Informed CRG community about the role of the Citizen Science Contact Point <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A Citizen Science Contact Point very engaged and enthusiastic about Citizen Science ● The guidelines (GA3) and new Citizen Science website information has been enriched and more tailored to researchers thanks to the implication of the Contact Point in their content creation ● Two research projects have incorporated Citizen Science elements in their scientific methodology
<p>6: Exploring how to assess Citizen Science activities in researchers' internal evaluations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agree on assess Citizen Science in internal evaluations ● Elaborating evaluation guidelines. ● Communicating the guidelines to the CRG community. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Head of the Strategy and Funding team ● Director 	<p>Output <i>(This GA is on-going)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Discussion about the impact of Citizen Science and how to incorporate it in internal evaluations ● The CRG plans to incorporated as a societal impact in internal evaluations processes <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Fruitful conversations with the director and the Head of the Strategy and Funding team about the types of impact of Citizen Science (societal, scientific) ● Awareness about the scientific impact of Citizen Science

5. Institutional Changes in KTU

5.1. Summary of TIME4CS outcomes in KTU

Kaunas University of Technology (KTU) is the largest technical university in the Baltic States. It seeks to become a strong science and innovation university, where the university studies are based on study and scientific research symbiosis.

Barriers for Citizen Science in KTU at the beginning of the project were:

On national level:

- The concept of Citizen Science was not widely used and understood in society. This was a huge barrier to motivate society to join Citizen Science projects.
- Weak motivation for citizens to engage in Citizen Science projects. As Citizen Science projects are volunteer-based activities, the difficult economic situation and emerging safety issues (influenced by Russian-Ukrainian war, Covid-19 pandemic, rising prices, etc.) did not motivate people to be part of volunteering activities in science.

Within institution:

- Weak motivation of scientists to initiate, develop and implement Citizen Science projects. The current situation was that there was not enough recognition of initiation/involvement in Citizen Science projects by the university
- Lack of competences in Citizen Science methodologies and approaches. Although the knowledge of Citizen Science methodologies was increasing among university researchers, still there was a space of improvement in this sphere.

Institutional support for Citizen Science at the beginning of the project

When we started the TIME4CS project, KTU was situated in a national context where the development of Citizen Science was just in the early adoption stage. But the university already had two strong Citizen Science champions, who had links to the national and international Citizen Science community and were responsible for the successful acquisition of seven Citizen Science projects. While the passion for Citizen Science sparked first interest in KTU amongst other researchers, there was no institutional support for this research methodology: There was no official training in Citizen Science for KTU researchers or support staff yet, no institutional policies, funding or a contact point financed by KTU to provide support for researchers. Therefore, the main aim of KTU in the TIME4CS project was to spread the awareness and knowledge about Citizen Science even further to researchers and the non-academic communities, institutionalise the links to the national and international communities and create a dedicated contact point as well as guidelines for Citizen Science to be fostered and more largely applied in KTU.

An overview of institutional support for Citizen Science at the beginning of the project is given in Figure 7.

KTU: Institutional Support – Starting Situation

Figure 7: KTU Institutional Support - Starting Situation

Institutional support for Citizen Science at the end of the project

The TIME4CS project helped to formalise the support for Citizen Science in KTU not only within the faculty for social sciences and arts, but on a university level. There were important institutional structures created and strategies on how to sustain them developed.

- Citizen science was integrated into courses for BA, MA, PhD students and research topics for post-docs. The Citizen Science course for researchers developed and officially certified.
- A Citizen Science strategy (guidelines) developed at a university level
- A virtual Citizen Science hub was established and a contact point for Citizen Science nominated and integrated into the university library to be open for all disciplines and the public to join the activities. The function of the Citizen Science contact point is funded.
- Organisational links to the Citizen Science Associations were formalised and deep involvement of the Citizen Science champions within KTU in the European and international Citizen Science community was established.
- KTU has run 15 Citizen Science projects so far, and submitted 5 Citizen Science proposals, counts 4 Citizen Science champions and an increasing number of researchers being involved in the Citizen Science activities.

The turning point also in this implementer organisation was the mentoring visit, when the management realised the potential of Citizen Science for the whole KTU and decided to create university wide guidelines

for Citizen Science and not only guidelines on the level of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities (FSSAH). Also, the idea to integrate the Citizen Science contact point to the library was initiated in this meeting.

Generally, the project supported reciprocal learning, networking, and creation of new Citizen Science proposals.

An overview of institutional support for Citizen Science at the end of the project is provided in Figure 8.

KTU: Institutional Support at the end of the project

Time4CS helped to further formalise CS across faculties and on a university level. There were important structures created and strategies on how to sustain them developed (e.g. CS contact point as part of the library, CS course for researchers certified, CS strategy developed at a university level). The project supported reciprocal learning, networking, and creation of new CS proposals.

Figure 8: KTU Institutional Support - End of TIME4CS Situation

5.2. Stock taking of institutional changes at the end of year 3

Intervention Area “Research”

KTU had 15 projects related to Citizen Science, thus this number increased by five compared to the last stock-taking exercise. These projects are:

- **H2020 project “Empowering Youth and Co-creating Social Innovations and Policy-Making Through Youth Citizen Social Science” (YOUCOUNT)¹¹**

¹¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101005931>

- **H2020 project “Supporting Sustainable Institutional Changes to Promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology” (TIME4CS)¹²**
- **H2020 project “ECIU University Research Institute for Smart European Regions (SMART-ER)¹³**
- Within SMART-ER, several new projects related to Citizen Science has been funded:
 - **“Citizen arenas for improved environmental quality and resource use in SMART-ER cities”,**
 - **“Establishing a Community on Empowering, Inclusive, and Equitable Citizen Science within ECIU” (ECIE)**
 - **“Research network resilient communities”**
- 2021-1-EE01-KA220-HED-000031125 project **University libraries strengthening the academia-society connection through Citizen Science in the Baltics (LibOCS)**
- ERASMUS-EDU-2022-EUR-UNIV-1 project **ECIU+**. 2022-2026.
- COST Action 17127 **“Building in Scientific Literacy in Evolution in Europe” (EuroScitizen)¹⁴.**
- COST Action CA15212 **“Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe”¹⁵**
- The European Union programme Erasmus+ project „**ECIU University**”. This project initiated several learning courses, including Citizen Science topics.
- National project **“Citizen Science as an Innovative Form of Citizen Participation for Welfare Society Development” (CS4Welfare)** funded by Research Council of Lithuania, 2020-2021
- National project **“Strengthening RESilience in Communities and sOCIety through citizeN sciEence and CiTizenship” (RECONNECT)**, funded by Research Council of Lithuania, 2023-2026
- Horizon Europe **“Promoting ocean and water literacy in school communities” (ProBleu)**, 2023-2026
- Erasmus+ project **“Empowering higher education through Citizen Science and innovative future oriented learning strategies”**, 2024-2027

Also, KTU scholars are constantly applying for Horizon Europe projects, also submitting proposals for Green Deal call, COST actions, which have a dimension of Citizen Science. Approximately, KTU submits **5 proposals related to Citizen Science per year**.

Among them, there are **three flagship initiatives**:

- H2020 project “ECIU University Research Institute for Smart European Regions (SMART-ER)”.
- H2020 project “Empowering Youth and Co-creating Social Innovations and Policy-Making Through Youth Citizen Social Science” (YOUCOUNT)
- H2020 project “Supporting Sustainable Institutional Changes to Promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology” (TIME4CS)

Also, the number of scientific publications related to Citizen Science increased within KTU. There are currently nine scientific publications, compared to five at the initial stock-taking.

¹² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006201>

¹³ <https://www.eciu.org/for-researchers/about#smart-er>

¹⁴ <http://www.euroscitizen.eu> ; <https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA17127/#tabs|Name:overview>

¹⁵ <https://cs-eu.net>

The publications, directly related to Citizen Science, are:

- Butkevičienė, Eglė; Mačiulienė, Monika; Mickevičiūtė, Evelina; Vaidelytė, Eglė; Vitkauskaitė-Ramanauskienė, Jonė; Balázs, Balint. Piliėčių mokslas kaip inovatyvi piliėčių dalyvavimo forma kuriant gerovės visuomenę : mokslo monografija. Kaunas: Technologija, 2022. 160 p. eISBN 9786090217702. DOI: 10.5755/e01.9786090217702.
- Mačiulienė, Monika; Butkevičienė, Eglė. The ecosystem approach in addressing sustainable development goals through Citizen Science in Lithuania // Sustainability. Basel : MDPI. ISSN 2071-1050. 2022, vol. 14, iss. 4, art. no. 2155, p. 1-14. DOI: 10.3390/su14042155. [Social Sciences Citation Index (Web of Science); Scopus; DOAJ] [IF: 3,251; AIF: 3,985; IF/AIF: 0,815; Q2 (2020, InCites JCR SSCI)] [CiteScore: 3,90; SNIP: 1,242; SJR: 0,612; Q1 (2020, Scopus Sources)]
- Klimczuk, Andrzej; Butkevičienė, Eglė; Kerla, Minela. Editorial: Citizen science and social innovation: mutual relations, barriers, needs, and development factors // Frontiers in sociology. Lausanne: Frontiers Media S.A. ISSN 2297-7775. 2022, vol. 7, art. no. 836149, p. 1-3. DOI: 10.3389/fsoc.2022.836149. [Emerging Sources Citation Index (Web of Science); Scopus; DOAJ] [CiteScore: 1,20; SNIP: 0,728; SJR: 0,000; Q2 (2020, Scopus Sources)]
- Butkevičienė, Eglė; Mačiulienė, Monika. Policy brief: recommendations for governance and ethics of Citizen Science projects // Piliėtinė visuomenė ir darnus vystymasis: tyrimų apžvalga = Civil society and sustainability: research brief / sudarytojai Florian Rabitz, Rasa Erentaitė, Laima Zakaraitė. Kaunas: Technologija. ISSN 2669-2554. 2022, no. 2, p. 24-27.
- Mačiulienė, Monika; Butkevičienė, Eglė; Vaidelytė, Eglė; Balázs, Balint. Co-creating social change through Citizen Science: systematic literature analysis // Filosofija. Sociologija = Philosophy, sociology. Vilnius : Lietuvos mokslų akademija. ISSN 0235-7186. eISSN 2424-4546. 2021, t. 32, Nr. 2, p. 159-168. DOI: 10.6001/fil-soc.v32i2.4416. [Social Sciences Citation Index (Web of Science); Arts & Humanities Citation Index (Web of Science); Scopus] [IF: 0,351; AIF: 2,450; IF/AIF: 0,143; Q4 (2020, InCites JCR SSCI)] [CiteScore 0,80; SNIP: 0,391; SJR: 0,214; Q2 (2020, Scopus Sources)]
- Tauginienė, Loreta; Butkevičienė, Eglė; Vohland, Katrin; Heinisch, Barbara; Daskolia, Maria; Suškevičs, Monika; Portela, Manuel; Balázs, Bálint; Průse, Baiba. Citizen science in the social sciences and humanities: the power of interdisciplinarity // Palgrave communications. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan. ISSN 2055-1045. 2020, vol. 6, iss. 1, art. no 89, p. 1-11. DOI: 10.1057/s41599-020-0471-y. [Emerging Sources Citation Index (Web of Science); Scopus; DOAJ] [CiteScore: 3,70; SNIP: 1,358; SJR: 0,613; Q1 (2020, Scopus Sources)]
- Butkevičienė, Eglė; Skarlatidou, Artemis; Balázs, Balint; Duží, Barbora; Massetti, Luciano; Tsampoulatidis, Ioannis; Tauginienė, Loreta. Citizen science case studies and their impacts on social innovation // The science of Citizen Science: [monograph] / editors K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, K. Wagenknecht. Cham: Springer, 2021. ISBN 9783030582777. eISBN 9783030582784. p. 309-329. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_16.
- Vohland, Katrin; Göbel, Claudia; Balázs, Balint; Butkevičienė, Eglė; Daskolia, Maria; Duží, Barbora; Hecker, Susanne; Manzoni, Marina; Schade, Sven. Citizen science in Europe // The science of Citizen Science: [monograph] / editors K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, K. Wagenknecht. Cham: Springer, 2021. ISBN 9783030582777. eISBN 9783030582784. p. 35-53. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_3.

- Albert, Alexandra; Balazs, Balint; Butkevičienė, Eglė; Mayer, Katja; Perelló, Josep. Citizen social science: new and established approaches to participation in social research // The science of Citizen Science: [monograph] / editors K. Vohland, A. Land-Zandstra, L. Ceccaroni, R. Lemmens, J. Perelló, M. Ponti, R. Samson, K. Wagenknecht. Cham: Springer, 2021. ISBN 9783030582777. eISBN 9783030582784. p. 119-138. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-58278-4_7.

Intervention Area “Education and Awareness”

The awareness and knowledge about Citizen Science among researchers in KTU is not very high yet, however a positive change is observable as it is constantly increasing. The expertise regarding Citizen Science methodologies is also quite low, but constantly increasing. The awareness of Citizen Science methodologies is higher among researchers from social sciences, but not among researchers representing natural sciences and engineering.

Data privacy issues fall under the responsibility and monitoring of the newly established (2020 November) Ethical Committee. This Committee is active and provides recommendations now to a major part of projects that require ethical approvals.

KTU also hosts a data archive, where there is a possibility to store data from Citizen Science projects. The KTU core team has already established the agreement to deposit such data to the archive.

A very positive change is also the increased number of formal and non-formal educational courses including Citizen Science topics, compared to a starting situation where no formal Citizen Science trainings were offered to KTU members.

There are different types of courses provided:

- For BA students: e.g., Citizen Science topic is incorporated in two modules “Civil society and volunteering” and “Basics of Science Communication”
- For MA students: e.g., Citizen Science topic is incorporated in a module “Public governance and civil society”
- For PhD students: e.g., Citizen Science topic is incorporated in modules such as “Science communication for the Public”, “Science, technology and society”, “Information society”.
- For international students/audiences: e.g., ICCS module (workshops on Intercultural Competences - Guiding Practical Insights through Citizen Science). This course was given to all students from ECIU universities (as free elective) in 2022, 2023 also planned for 2024.
- For the general public: e.g., “Opportunities and challenges in developing Citizen Science projects”.

The textbook/learning materials about the use of Citizen Science is forthcoming, most probably as part of a sustainability plan after the project implementation.

The communication about the Citizen Science initiatives on institutional channels is slightly improving. The ECIU university website has links to the Citizen Science initiatives now, but they are more addressed to researchers rather than to general public¹⁶.

But the bigger communication campaign is foreseen as one of the activities of virtual Citizen Science hub (PMC - Piliėčių mokslo inkubatorius = Citizen Science hub”) and thus part of a TIME4CS Grounding Action “Sustainability”.

A positive change can also be observed regarding the number of discussions about Citizen Science organised by KTU.

- For example, there was a practice sharing seminar organised in Kaunas, KTU, in Lithuanian language, where external stakeholders were invited to discuss Citizen Science perspectives and needs for Citizen Science. Thus, this event was both a training and a dialogue creation activity.¹⁷
- On 2nd December 2022, KTU organised a national seminar: a round table discussion at the conference of the Lithuanian Sociological Association on Citizen Science and institutional changes. This discussion was initiated by the TIME4CS project (KTU team).

In 2023, TIME4CS results were presented at several conferences:

- Cit*Sci conference (Arizona, US)
- International conference “Connect. Collaborate. Co-Create” (Paris, France)
- SMART-ER final conference (Barcelona, Spain)

Intervention Area “Support resources & infrastructures”

Since the first stock-taking exercise KTU has become an institutional member of the national Citizen Science association (Lithuania) as well as of ECSA.

- **ECSA:** KTU is an institutional member of ECSA. Egle Butkeviciene is mainly engaged in three working groups: 1) Working group on “Empowerment, Inclusiveness and Equity”, 2) Working group on “Storytelling and other arts”, 3) Working group on “Citizen science and universities”. In 2022 she also joined the Working group on “Agri-food”. In 2023 she volunteered to act as a co-chair of WG “Citizen science and open science”.
- **Piliėčių mokslo asociacija (national Citizen Science association):** Egle Butkeviciene is a founding member of the national Citizen Science association. Monika Mačiulienė, who was a post-doc and currently is a senior researcher in KTU is a founding member and a head of this association. KTU is an institutional member.

¹⁶ <https://www.eciu.org/smart-er-for-researchers#citizen-science>

¹⁷ <https://data.ktu.edu/course/2022-m-lapkricio-28-d-patirties-dalinimosi-seminaras-pilieciu-mokslo-projektu-rengimo-galimybes-ir-issukiai>

Next to the two Citizen Science champions, who were mentioned above and are very well connected with other organisations and networks related to Citizen Science, participating in ECSA, joining advisory boards of other projects, like SOCIO-BEE¹⁸, INCENTIVE¹⁹ and ECS²⁰.

There are other members of KTU slowly reaching out, engaging in Citizen Science related projects that exist in the institution, like YouCount, TIME4CS, LibOCS, SMART-ER.

However, there is still no substantial representation of KTU in national, European-wide and international committees related to Citizen Science.

What has positively changed is the number of Citizen Science champions in KTU. Last year KTU counted two Citizen Science champions and this number increased to four persons, representing Sociology, Education sciences and Communication studies. Citizen science is only part of an employee's job description if they are employed by one of the Citizen Science related projects.

But there is good progress in the establishment of a virtual Citizen Science hub, which is part of the TIME4CS Grounding Actions and will rely on external funding mainly.

There are no major changes from last years' stock-taking exercise when we look at funding for Citizen Science, except that KTU got funding from the Research Council of Lithuania to implement national-wide the project "Strengthening REsilience in Communities and sOciety through citizeN sciEnce and CiTizenship" (RECONNECT), which started in September 2023 and Erasmus+ project "Empowering higher education through Citizen Science and innovative future oriented learning strategies", that will start in 2024. Different funding opportunities are available under Horizon Europe programs, also national programs coordinated by Research Council of Lithuania and the 2014–2020 Operational Programme for the European Union Funds' Investments in Lithuania. KTU is constantly submitting proposals to these calls (for example, addressing the call Twinning (HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02) in 2023 or other similar calls).

The Internal Research and Innovation Fund of KTU also funds research projects in different thematics including civil society building and resilient communities.

What changed compared to last year is the initiative among ECIU consortium partners to fund Citizen Science pilots, where KTU participates in 3 of such projects.

As of last year, researchers of KTU have access to the open data archive "Lithuanian Data Archive for Social Sciences and Humanities (LiDA)"²¹. The archive is ready to deposit quantitative and qualitative data sets, also including data from Citizen Science projects.

KTU has an established practice and needed infrastructures to foster open science. KTU is a member of the European Open Science network "OpenAIRE"²² that builds open science policies for the European Commission, provides training and contributes to developing open science services and infrastructures. The KTU representative is the OpenAIRE National Open Access Desk coordinator.

¹⁸ <https://socio-bee.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://incentive-project.eu>

²⁰ <https://eu-citizen.science/>

²¹ <https://lida.dataverse.lt/>

²² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

Intervention Area “Policy & Assessment”

There are no major changes in the Intervention Area of “Policy and Assessment”: In 2021 KTU adopted the KTU Strategy for 2021 – 2025 and the Action Plan 2021 – 2025 to implement this strategy. The document of open access to scientific publications and research data at KTU was approved in 2020. These documents do not explicitly include Citizen Science, but science communication and public engagement is integrated in all these documents.

Science communication is one of the elements that is evaluated during the attestation of researchers and university teachers (for the position of professor, associate professor, chief researcher, and senior researcher).

Public engagement and societal impact (where Citizen Science is a contributor and catalyst for impact and engagement) are assessed as part of a national comparative qualitative evaluation of Lithuanian higher education institutions’ research units, conducted every five years. Institutions are developing impact cases that must make explicit the public engagement activities and the impact achieved.

A positive change since the last year can be observed at the KTU management level, where due to the TIME4CS project activities a higher level of awareness for Citizen Science can be observed.

The KTU management has a positive opinion towards the importance of Citizen Science for the university activities and encouraged researchers to participate in SMART-ER project pilots of Citizen Science.

In 2023 KTU developed the Guidelines for Citizen Science at the university level and currently they are in the approval stage.

5.3. Overview of GAs, outputs and outcomes

In the previous section we have introduced the main institutional changes to support Citizen Science in KTU. In this section we take a closer look at the Grounding Actions, their expected and partly realised outcomes and impacts at the time of writing this deliverable (Table 3).

Table 3: Evaluation model of KTU

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
1. To establish connections with Citizen Science networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Initiating membership application in ECSA ● Initiating membership application in national Citizen Science association. ● Initiating cooperation with Eu-citizen.science platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● KTU Research communities 	Output: 2 memberships established: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 in ECSA, ● 1 in the National Citizen Science Association Active engagement in 5 ECSA working groups. Advisory Board member of ECS project that is taking care of Eu-citizen.science platform.

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
<p>2. To expand research projects using Citizen Science methodology and involve a greater diversity of researchers into research project proposals in Citizen Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing and disseminating research priorities related to Citizen Science and open science at the FSSAH Organising co-creation workshops for writing project proposals on Citizen Science topic or using Citizen Science methodology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core team KTU Research communities from different faculties and at different level of their career 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research priorities defined 4 co-creation workshops organised over 10 participants in the workshops 3 co-created proposals related to Citizen Science: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 COST, 2 SMART-ER internal, 5 Horizon Europe 2 National programme
<p>3. To disseminate research results on Citizen Science through different academic channels</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> organising a national seminar to share research results Presenting research findings at international conferences Using media to disseminate research results to a wider public. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core team KTU Research communities involved in Citizen Science 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 national seminar organised on 2 December 2022 (round table discussion) Over 30 of participants in the national seminar 10 presentations about Citizen Science at international conferences (2021-2023) 2 poster presentations 3 media contributions on Citizen Science
<p>4.1 To develop a non-formal educational programme to researchers of all career stages</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> organise co-creation sessions for developing the non-formal educational programs. Disseminate the call for non-formal educational programs Introduce the Citizen Science topic in existing identified formal educational programs and courses within KTU. Integrate the non-formal educational programs with the already established DAtA centre Methods' School²³. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core team KTU Research communities 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creation sessions to develop non-formal education programme for researchers organised 1 non-formal education programme for researchers created, officially registered and integrated into DAtA centre Methods' School Dissemination of the call for non-formal educational programs²⁴ 1 non-formal education course held on 11 January, 2023 (3 hours of content delivery) Over 15 participants trained

²³ <https://data.ktu.edu/courses/buve-mokymai/>

²⁴ <https://shmmf.ktu.edu/events/data-centro-mokymai-pilieciu-mokslo-pagrindai/>

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
<p>4.2 To develop a non-formal educational programme for citizens and non-academic stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> organise co-creation sessions for developing the MOOC Develop the MOOC platform and content Disseminate the MOOC Organise one MOOC session Collect feedback Prepare and publish a Lithuanian textbook on Citizen Science methodology to further support the non-formal and formal education programs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core team local/territorial communities; school communities; various non-governmental organisations in Lithuania; other not-for-profit and business organisations, whose members are willing to engage with Citizen Science 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-creation session to develop non-formal education programme for non-academics organised 1 non-formal education programme for non-academics created, officially registered and integrated into DATA center Methods' School Dissemination of the call for non-formal educational programs²⁵ <p>Planned trainings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 non-formal education held on 12 January, 2023 (3 hours of content delivery) Over 15 participants trained

²⁵ <https://shmmf.ktu.edu/events/data-centro-mokymai-pilieciu-mokslo-pagrindai/>
<https://data.ktu.edu/course/2023-m-sausio-11-d-mokymai-pilieciu-mokslo-taikymas-moksliniuose-tyrimuose/>

Planned activities	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
<p>Virtual Hub and University Contact Point for Citizen Science Projects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> organise consultation session about the establishment of Citizen Science hub with the Dean's office of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities. Establishment of the Citizen Science Virtual Hub as a third level unit within the Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities Opening the section on the Citizen Science projects as part of the www.data.ktu.lt website Appointing the Contact Point for the Citizen Science projects organise discussion of the functions and the facilitation scope of the Contact Point Develop and adopt a feasibility study on Virtual Hub's funding and resource mobilization, accompanied with two-year activity plans. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core team KTU Research communities from different faculties school communities, NGOs etc. dean's office of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities University Rector's office 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consultation session with Dean's office organised Concept of the functions of the Virtual Hub defined Approval by the Dean's office regarding the establishment of Citizen Science Virtual Hub Citizen science Virtual Hub moved to KTU Library
<p>Strategic Citizen Science guidelines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consultations with stakeholders regarding the development of Citizen Science guidelines at KTU. Development of Citizen Science guidelines. Adoption of Citizen Science guidelines on the university level. Dissemination of Citizen Science guidelines for KTU community through internal KTU communication tools. Presentation of Citizen Science guidelines for KTU community during info-sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core team KTU admin Representatives from Research Department and Research and Innovation Projects Centre KTU Legal Department Students and researchers 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 Consultations with stakeholders regarding the development of Citizen Science guidelines at KTU Citizen Science guidelines developed

6. Institutional Changes in Tyndall

6.1. Summary of TIME4CS outcomes in Tyndall

Tyndall National Institute is part of the University College Cork (UCC) and a leading research centre in integrated ICT hardware and systems. The institute receives a large amount of funding from EU and local funding agencies such as Science Foundation Ireland (SFI), Irish Research Council (IRC) and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA).

Barriers that hinder Citizen Science to become an accepted researcher approach within Tyndall include missing capacity building to support researchers' involvement in Citizen Science initiatives. Training at student and staff level is a necessary step to increase Citizen Science uptake. Citizen science projects involve partnership with communities and NGOs, and capacity building for external stakeholders is required. Citizen science is often interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research, which is hugely beneficial but again requires capacity building support.

There is probably some reluctance against the inclusion of Citizen Science aspects, due to the researchers' lack of knowledge on how to structure, run and manage these types of projects.

Tyndall is physically isolated from the main UCC campus and often not on the "radar" of large initiatives that are not specifically ICT driven. This barrier has been lowered during the last two years, but more work is necessary to facilitate communication and flow of ideas/complementary expertise.

Institutional support for Citizen Science at the beginning of the project

When starting with the TIME4CS project 3 years ago, Tyndall researchers did not have any knowledge and experiences in Citizen Science yet, as the topic of research - specialising in both electronics and photonics - made it a challenge to actively involve citizens in research. There were no Citizen Science projects, no champions or contact points for Citizen Science in Tyndall. But there were Citizen Science projects, researchers and infrastructures that support the active public engagement in the wider area of UCC. Thus, the aim for the TIME4CS project was to benefit from the experiences of UCC, increase awareness and knowledge for Citizen Science amongst Tyndall researchers, raise awareness for potential Citizen Science funding opportunities, and promote and support submissions that incorporate the Citizen Science dimensions in order to have first good practice examples in Tyndall.

Figure 9 presents an overview of institutional support for Citizen Science in Tyndall at the beginning of the project.

Tyndall: Institutional Support - Starting situation

Figure 9: Tyndall Institutional Support - Starting Situation

Institutional support for Citizen Science at the end of the project

Starting from a situation with no institutional support for Citizen Science at all, Tyndall has made considerable advancements in the last 3 years. The TIME4CS Grounding Actions supported establishing links to the UCC community manager and Citizen Science support activities in UCC, to connect with other institutions, like RPOs, RFOs, interested NGOs involved in Citizen Science in Ireland, and to raise awareness for Citizen Science and engaged research within Tyndall. A real “game changer” in the whole process was the mentoring visit with a very nice representation of higher management from UCC, Tyndall and Science Foundation Ireland (SFI) being present and the management realising the high potential of Citizen Science for their research institutions. Part of this mentoring visit were hands-on workshops with some selected researchers, starting to co-create very small projects for Citizen Science together. This was a very good way of finding the hook for researchers to understand how they can use Citizen Science for their specific research.

There were important institutional structures created and strategies on how to sustain them developed.

- Tyndall has its own community officer now, who is responsible to support researchers conducting EPE (Education and Public Engagement) activities. This new position shows the recognition at management level for this new research approach.
- A postgraduate training module on Citizen Science was conceptualised, containing 12 hours of teaching and 12 hours of hands-on exercises related to Citizen Science in Tyndall. This module was now officially accepted and will be implemented, disseminated and rolled out in the next months.

- The involvement of communities in research on light and photonics is now very well embedded in the research plan of IPIC, the SFI Research Centre for photonics. The Tyndall and UCC team developed a preliminary draft of the Engaged Research Strategy, to be adopted as part of UCC’s Strategic Plan.
- In the new building of Tyndall, which will be constructed in the next three years, there will be an extra space open to the public, with a café and a living lab. It’s due to the Tyndall team who insisted on this open space for the public, that this concept will be realised.
- At a UCC level, there are concrete plans and funding to establish a Citizen Science support group, comparable to the Citizen Science Centre Zurich (one of the Front-Runners in TIME4CS). This group will not only offer support for researchers in applying for and conducting Citizen Science projects, but also training for researchers. These training modules will be compulsory for young researchers to gain promotion.

Figure 10 presents an overview of institutional support for Citizen Science at the end of the TIME4CS project.

Tyndall: Institutional Support at the end of the project

Time4CS supported establishing links to the UCC community manager and CS support activities in UCC, to connect with other institutions involved in CS in Ireland and to raise awareness for CS and engaged research within Tyndall. First institutional changes relate to the funding of a Tyndall community manager, the creation of the CS postgraduate course and the elaboration of the Engaged Research Strategy.

Figure 10: Tyndall Institutional Support - End Situation

6.2. Stock taking of institutional changes at the end of year 3

In the last two years, Tyndall has witnessed a growing interest for Citizen Science, which in Ireland is one of the recognized approaches under the national Engaged Research priority of our National Research and Innovation Strategy 2021-2027. Engaged Research is used in Ireland as an umbrella term for a wide range of rigorous research approaches and methodologies that share a common interest in collaborative engagement with society.

One of the triggers for advancing Citizen Science is institutional level recognition and support. To achieve this, Tyndall has received the active engagement of the UCC Head of Civic and Community Engagement, Dr. Martin Galvin (established through TIME4CS activities). Through Martin, Citizen Science has been prioritised under UCC's Engaged Research activities, including the new University Strategic Plan 2023-2028. Engaged Research and Citizen Science form a key component of the UNIC European University Alliance, which is a partnership of 10 European Universities and their Cities. UCC is leading an Engaged Research Strategy, inclusive of Citizen Science, for this alliance. A CityLab (Living Lab) has been established in Cork, which is supporting a wide range of citizen engagement in research activities²⁶.

Via Martin, Tyndall is connecting with a number of researchers in the wider UCC community and increasing the opportunities to participate in collaborative and interdisciplinary projects, with aspects of Citizen Science. Engaged Research and Citizen Science have also been placed as a priority for Tyndall's new Community Officer, Eamonn O'Sullivan, who works closely with Martin on the establishment of ways to engage rural and local communities in the areas of photonics and communication. A new Engaged Research Officer has been appointed under the UCC Vice President for Research and new training in Engaged Research are being rolled out in UCC this year, of which Tyndall and Citizen Science have visibility, often because of the connection with Martin. The topics of Engaged Research, social innovation and inclusion are more often part of large collaborative projects under preparation (both at EU and national levels). In parallel, Tyndall is now moving through the "training" phase with the development of a TIME4CS Citizen Science module for postgraduate students and the train-the-trainer programmes targeted to EPE officers and community officers. These are necessary steps to lower the barriers into Citizen Science inclusion in research projects.

Intervention Area "Research"

Compared to the first stock taking exercise, there is now a first Citizen Science project by a Tyndall researcher and more researcher proposals with Citizen Science aspects have been written in Tyndall. Thus, Citizen Science is a growing field of activity within Tyndall.

This first Citizen Science project is Uiscope, a device-enabled Citizen Science project on water quality led by a researcher at Tyndall National Institute.

In UCC the range of Citizen Science activities has even grown compared to the last stock-taking exercise, some are listed below.

- Science for Clean Water and Sanitation.

²⁶ <https://www.unic.eu/en/city-labs>

- Citizen Science Stream Index
- Nature-Watch
- All Ireland Ladybird online survey
- Crowd4Access
- A-AAGORA
- Dingle Peninsula 2030, a national flagship initiative, was established in 2018 as a multi-partner engaged research and Citizen Science initiative on the Dingle Peninsula, Co. Kerry, involving the Dingle Creativity and Innovation Hub, ESB Networks, North East and West Kerry Development (NEWKD), and UCC MaREI Research Centre. The premise is based on the Quadruple Helix Model involving science, policy, industry, and society. Partners are actively collaborating with the local community, schools, business, transport, and farming sectors to enable the broader societal changes required for the sustainable transition²⁷. This initiative has won multiple awards which are displayed on its website and was featured in a Television Documentary on RTE 1 our national broadcaster.²⁸

In connection to these research activities there are hundreds of publications from UCC researchers.

Intervention area “Education and Awareness”

In UCC and nationally, awareness of Engaged Research is a developing field, within this there is a high degree of awareness regarding Public and Patient Involvement (PPI) research approaches and methodologies. Prioritising Engaged Research and Citizen Science within UCC’s new Strategic Plan 2023-2028 will significantly advance awareness of Citizen Science amongst UCC researchers. UCC has a long tradition of offering training and education in Engaged Research for staff. They have a dedicated Engaged Research Officer based in the Research Office, a whole university professional development plan for engaged research is being developed. Training in Engaged Research is being offered as part of the UNIC European University initiative. The Cork CityLab is providing training and capacity development in co-creation methods. UCC has a Citizen Science session within the “PG6029: Skills in science communication” module for postgraduate students. Training (half day) on Engaged research and Research integrity & Ethics are run periodically for researchers by the UCC Research Office. Nationally, UCC collaborates with all of the Irish Universities to develop and provide training under the auspices of the Irish Universities Association Campus Engage initiative²⁹. Campus Engage offered an Engaged Research & Innovation for Societal Impact 6-Week Online Course in 2023. Martin Galvin is a national Engaged Research Educator and 2 UCC staff are now qualified as national trainers.

Within Tyndall, Citizen Science is a developing field, with a need to build awareness and capacity, which is still perceived as low to medium.

Many Tyndall students have taken the UCC Postgraduate module on science communication the past two years, so would have experienced the 2-3 hour session on Citizen Science within this module. In addition Tyndall is just developing specific training sessions in the scope of the TIME4CS project that will be launched in 2024.

²⁷ <https://www.marei.ie/project/dingle-peninsula-2030>

²⁸ <https://www.iaa.ie/changemakers/dingle-peninsula-2030-ucc/>

²⁹ www.campusengage.ie

Intervention Area “Support resources and infrastructures”

As has already been mentioned, UCC is active in the field of Engaged Research, linking with a wide range of organisations and networks. The UNIC European University initiative has linked UCC with universities who are very active in Citizen Science, particularly Bochum University in Germany. The UNIC CityLabs initiative engages researchers in opportunities to co-create research with external stakeholders. The PPI Ignite Network in UCC, similarly supports research engagement with societal partners³⁰. Other SFI centres in UCC work on Citizen Science/community based projects and so they have contacts there. UCC is also an institutional member of ECSA and CSA. They are also an institutional member of the Talloires Network and Campus Engage.

As a result of all these successful Citizen Science activities and collaborations to other organisations, in UCC there are several Citizen Science champions who also cover different fields of research (e.g. business & law, environmental science, marine biology). UCC has for example a Civic and Community Engagement Committee and a Head of Civic and Community Engagement, an Engaged Research Officer, an Engaged Learning Officer, CityLabs Coordinator, Graduate Attributes Manager, Local Neighborhood Liaison Officer, and part time support staff. There are 2 people centrally in UCC, who have Citizen Science in their job description: Martin Galvin and John Barimo. In addition, there is a wider group of EPE Officers in the SFI funded Centres who have a specific support remit around Engaged Research.

UCC is currently working toward the establishment of a support unit for engaged research in the research office, inclusive of Citizen Science. And they are working towards a high level working group to provide direction and strategy on engaged research in UCC, inclusive of Citizen Science.

In Tyndall, connections are intensified to UCC researchers engaged in Citizen Science. Some researchers in Tyndall also have collaborations and/or funding with the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) who is active in Citizen Science. Very important is that Tyndall has a new community officer, Eamonn O’Sullivan, who has started making contacts with rural and local communities towards the development of joint projects in the areas of communication and biophotonics. There is no specific contact point for Citizen Science in Tyndall.

There is no internal funding for Citizen Science activities in Tyndall, but there is funding for Citizen Science projects via the SFI Discover Programme³¹ and UCC received a number of SFI Discover grants. In addition, as part of the UNIC European University initiative a €400.000 seed fund scheme for Engaged Research has been established. Locally there are Engaged Research seed fund schemes in the APC Microbiome Ireland SFI Research Centre and MaREI SFI Research Centre for Energy, Climate and Marine.

³⁰ <https://www.ucc.ie/en/ppi-ignite/>

³¹ <https://www.sfi.ie/funding/funding-calls/sfi-discover-programme/>

Intervention area “Policy and Assessment”

Science communication and public engagement is integrated in UCC’s and Tyndall’s institutional research strategy and mandated by SFI funding. UCC has data management, open access publication, data provenance and intellectual properties as part of the wider research policies. There is a contact point for Open Science. There is a Civic and Community Engagement plan to be revised and updated in 2023. This will include a significant section on Engaged Research and Citizen Science. Engaged Research, RRI and Open Science will form one of 5 strategic goals for research in the new University strategy 2023-2028 and Tyndall will be incorporated into this strategy as part of UCC.

Research evaluation:

UCC has an “Engaged Research of the Year” category in the Annual Research Awards. Tyndall has introduced this year its own Awards with one category dedicated to “Education & Public Awareness”. SFI also has annual awards for Engaged Research for researchers holding SFI grants.

In UCC, external engagement and external community service is part of academic promotions at all grade levels with a significant proportion of marks attributed.

In Tyndall, the active involvement of citizens in scientific projects is considered in the annual Performance Evaluation Exercise, but there are no marks. If a new position is created, engagement is taken into consideration and constitutes a bonus, but it does not constitute a criterion for employment.

In Tyndall, researchers are being encouraged institutionally to take part in public engagement activities. It’s mentioned in the job description of most contracts internally the last 2-3 years, it is just not Citizen Science specific. As mentioned, Citizen Science can fall under the very large umbrella of different public engagement activities you could do, but it’s also a special specific area in itself. Societal engagement via research and teaching is part of academic promotion criteria. Furthermore, researchers at all levels (from PhD to PI) funded by SFI need to perform two EPE activities per year. These are captured by an automated system and used by SFI for their national statistics. Every year researchers have a performance evaluation, and it is well perceived if researchers participated in public engagement activities. Also in any new contracts, as student or staff member, Tyndall members must participate in public engagement and there is the commitment from their supervisors to allow students and researchers to do the public engagement work. So public engagement activities are important but not specific to Citizen Science.

UCC has a Vice President External Relations on their University Management Team, who will now be replaced by a Vice President Global Engagement with responsibility for local, national, global engagement. There is also a Vice President Research who is passionate about Engaged Research in all its forms.

In Tyndall, there is a new community officer, who was already introduced before and will take some management role in time.

6.3. Overview of GAs, outputs and outcomes

In the previous section we have introduced the main institutional changes to support Citizen Science in Tyndall. In this section we take a closer look at the Grounding Actions, their outcomes and impacts at the end of the TIME4CS project (Table 4).

Table 4: Evaluation model of Tyndall

Grounding Actions	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
<p>1. Promoting and supporting incorporation of Citizen Science dimension into research projects</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify funding calls particularly benefitting from Citizen Science dimension ● Raise awareness of Citizen Science-based calls among Tyndall researchers ● Build national and international network of collaborators ● Identify and participate in international conferences ● Liaise with funding agencies (SFI, IRC) into the implementation of policies incorporating Citizen Science dimension into research projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SFI centres ● EPE officers ● Funding agencies ● Tyndall researchers ● UCC researchers 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 3 quarterly meetings to discuss funding calls in 2022 ● 1 interdisciplinary workshop with researchers in 2022 ● Monthly TIME4CS Tyndall meetings with 3-4 people involved; ● 1 developed proposal with a Citizen Science dimension <p>Outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Meetings are perceived as useful to monitor progress and scope opportunities. ● To gain knowledge of wider opportunities within UCC and abroad. <p>Participants report about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increases of awareness and knowledge due to participation in meetings and workshops. ● Extension of networks relevant to implement Citizen Science (with internal and external researchers; with community members) ● New collaborations with the dept of computer science and architecture have been established.
<p>2. Create a postgraduate module on Citizen Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Assemble an extended “production” team interested in the development of the module ● Reach out to the wider stakeholder community; Co-design of module length, format and delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● Extended production team ● SEFS managing team (consulting and impacted) ● Graduate studies committee of 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 3-6 people involved in the content production of the postgraduate module ● 12 hours of teaching and ● 12 hours of field work elaborated <p>The module will roll out in Sept 2024. The targeted No. of students is: 6-15</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collect information from a wider UCC team on existing material for relevant complementary courses ● Assembly of course and delivery ● Discuss and implement a sustainability plan; 	<p>Tyndall and UCC ((impacted)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Postgraduate students (impacted) 	
<p>3. Elaborate a training program for researchers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Internal Dissemination of TIME4CS project ● Assembly and delivery of a general Citizen Science presentation for Tyndall researchers, linked to TIME4CS ● Gather interest in Citizen Science through promotion of seed projects ● Organisation of training modules for researchers ● Work in close collaboration with CONNECT 2 and the Academy of the Near Future to organise workshops and raise awareness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● Extended team ● Tyndall researchers (impacted) ● Tyndall high management (impacted) ● Trainers (impacted) ● Extended team with Trinity-based Academy 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 2 Citizen Science presentations ● 1 Citizen Science workshops ● > 30 participants in presentations and workshops ● Presentations on Citizen Science and TIME4CS created ● Citizen Science workshop (November 2023) for CONNECT 2 researchers <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Good feedback and questions received in the workshops and presentations ● Knowledge on Citizen Science is still low but first awareness for Citizen Science is generated. <p>Participants report about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased interest to implement Citizen Science and realisation of strategic need
<p>4. Funding Awareness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organise interdisciplinary seminars ● Identify humanities-based projects requiring scientific inputs (discussing engagement with disadvantaged schools to enhance the quality of STEM teaching in Gaelic) funded by Higher Education Authority 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● UCC humanities staff, ● Tyndall staff, ● SFI centres and ● EPE officers 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 2 interdisciplinary seminars ● 10 participants in the seminars <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Good feedback and interest in collaborations <p>Participants report about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Growing awareness about funding opportunities with support offered ● Growing interest to develop Citizen Science projects
<p>5. Supporting the development of an engaged research strategy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Organise an Engaged Research Strategy Forum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UCC Engaged Research Strategy ● Citizen Science Extended Team 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 10 people participating in the Engaged Research Strategy Forum ● Development of a preliminary draft of the Engaged Research Strategy, to be adopted as part of UCC's Strategic Plan

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Map current institutional practices, policies and initiatives for Engaged Research and Citizen Science • Develop a common institutional understanding of Engaged Research and Citizen Science • Define and develop a (Preliminary) Engaged Research Strategy (inclusive of Citizen Science) • Sign an institutional and external partner Declaration on Engaged Research (inclusive of Citizen Science) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Substantial grant obtained by UCC to implement a pilot scheme around ER • Dedicated co-creation, maker space and café in the new Tyndall building
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7. Institutional Changes in UniSR

7.1. Summary of TIME4CS outcomes in UniSR

Vita-Salute San Raffaele University (UniSR) is characterised by a strong integration of teaching and research and is part of the Gruppo Ospedaliero San Donato. Thus, in UniSR the vast majority of the research activities are in biomedicine, including a substantial proportion of work in clinical research. These areas are typically less amenable to Citizen Science approaches (also due to privacy and ethical concerns), and require additional effort to identify appropriate activities. On the other hand, UniSR has a limited number of researchers in the areas of psychology and philosophy, who are more open to Citizen Science approaches. Next to the specific research area that makes the active involvement of citizens in research a challenge, researchers have insufficient knowledge of Citizen Science approaches, methodologies and benefits.

Institutional support for Citizen Science at the beginning of the project

UniSR is involved in research topics that do not link so easily to Citizen Science approaches. Thus, in UniSR there were no Citizen Science projects implemented when starting TIME4CS, nor were there any training, Citizen Science champions or a contact point for Citizen Science yet. Also, there was a lack of institutional, financial and logistic support to the Citizen Science activities. However, UniSR had participatory projects with “expert patients”. These projects did not consider themselves to be Citizen Science, but have already actively involved patients into training, presentation and discussion of research results. In addition, there were three H2020 projects that contained elements of Citizen Science without calling themselves Citizen Science. Thus, when implementing the Grounding Actions, links should be established to these projects and researchers. For UniSR, it was important to raise the knowledge and awareness for Citizen Science amongst researchers via training and informal get-togethers, to establish a Citizen Science contact point and create first linkages to the national/international Citizen Science community.

Figure 11 presents an overview of institutional support for Citizen Science in UniSR at the beginning of the project.

UniSR: Institutional Support - Starting situation

Figure 11: UniSR Institutional Support - Starting Situation

Institutional support for Citizen Science at the end of the project

Starting from a situation with no institutional support for Citizen Science at all, also UniSR could implement considerable institutional changes in the last 3 years. Or as one of the UniSR colleagues mentioned in the evaluation workshop “TIME4CS kicked off the institutional changes to support Citizen Science and it cannot be stopped now.”

Representatives of different departments started to work together and created new structures internally to allow for Citizen Science to sustain and further develop. They worked together on:

- The elaboration of institutional guidelines for Citizen Science projects
- The preparation of a Citizen Science section with material and resources on Citizen Science on the UniSR intranet
- The implementation of a Citizen Science session in courses for students of the *Master's Degree in Nursing and Midwifery*, of the *Master's degree in Communication of Science and Health*, and PhD students. The provision of this Citizen Science session to the whole UniSR team online.
- The preparation and dissemination of monthly Citizen Science newsletters called “Bits of Citizen Science” which is distributed to 2000 recipients
- The conduction of four “Science and Society” seminars targeted at researchers to spark interest in public engagement in research

- The provision of a contact point e-mail address which is supported by the whole core team, as well as the nomination of a dedicated Citizen Science contact point.
- The elaboration of evaluation criteria on Citizen Science that are integrated to researchers' evaluation as soon as they are approved.

Also, in UniSR, the mentoring visit was a key element in the change process. The talks and training organised by the TIME4CS frontrunners motivated the UniSR core team to actively approach their researchers and invite them to the sessions. The hands-on practical exercises of the mentoring and training visit resulted in concrete ideas for Citizen Science projects and first multipliers amongst the researchers to sustain the activities.

Figure 12 presents the institutional support at the end of the project.

UniSR: Institutional Support at the end of the project

Figure 12: UniSR Institutional Support - End Situation

Concrete triggers for Citizen Science in UniSR in future are:

- Effective and concrete communication to researchers about Citizen Science as a research method.
- Focused training with practical examples of Citizen Science in biomedicine as the first step.

- Supporting services for interested researchers offered by institutional offices/bodies.
- Incentives for stimulating Citizen Science activities.
- Institutional commitment and effort.

7.2. Stock taking of institutional changes at the end of year 3

Intervention Area “Research”

At the start of the TIME4CS project, UniSR had already been a member of three H2020 projects that contained elements of the Citizen Science approach without labelling them as such (PERITIA³², RENergetic³³ and SMART-Bear³⁴). During the last year some Citizen Science-related initiatives have been started and implemented. These initiatives are detailed here below:

- Uni4Me³⁵: this is a project developed in UniSR, focused on studying the correlation between detected levels of heavy metals and lifestyle. The project has been implemented through the engagement of students who play an active role in the study design and its execution.
- DRItti a Voi: in February 2024 there will be a large event, organised by the Diabetes Research Institute (DRI), fully dedicated to the patients and their families. In collaboration with the patients’ association Diabete Italia, with the support of the UniSR core team, DRI is planning to have a Citizen Science action: a questionnaire provided to patients in order to investigate some key questions and unmet patients’ needs.
- A project on patients with cystic fibrosis: a San Raffaele research group focused on cystic fibrosis is planning to co-create a questionnaire with patients to investigate both lifestyle and impact of the new therapies used for treating cystic fibrosis.
- Stomycraft³⁶: a game developed by a UniSR researcher in nursing, together with the association of patients with ostomy FAIS - Federazione Associazioni Incontinenti e Stomizzati. Children with ostomy can play with the game receiving guidelines, support and motivation to treat the ostomy in the correct way.

In addition to the above-mentioned Citizen Science projects, UniSR can count more initiatives dedicated to public engagement, some of which are listed in the Annex 1 to this document.

With regard to Citizen Science, UniSRreport only one publication with a focus on patient engagement, entitled “Communication and Patient Engagement at Diagnosis of Pancreatic Cancer”, published in 2020.

In the course of the TIME4CS project, UniSR has started to reach out to other organisations involved in Citizen Science. UniSR joined the two ECSA working groups on Citizen Science for Health and Citizen Science and Universities as an active member. Following the same approach, UniSR has also joined the ECSA working

³² <https://peritia-trust.eu/>

³³ <http://www.renergetic.eu/>

³⁴ <https://www.smart-bear.eu/>

³⁵ https://www.instagram.com/unisr_uni4me/

³⁶ <https://stomycraft.org/>

group on Storytelling and other Arts. UniSR also participated in the first Citizen Science for Health Conference in November 2023.

Intervention Area “Education and awareness”

As mentioned above, the knowledge and interest in Citizen Science among UniSR researchers is generally low with a few exceptions in some research groups. Although a few researchers, as described above, have recently launched Citizen Science initiatives, in some cases there is a negative view of Citizen Science as it is perceived as an intrusion of “poorly knowledgeable” citizens into research, with the risk of biased results. Targeted educational activities are key to counteract these fears.

In comparison to the initial stock-taking exercise at the beginning of TIME4CS, UniSR has in the meantime organised first initiatives related to Citizen Science, as part of the TIME4CS Grounding Actions.

- 1) The series of seminars called “Science and Society”, launched in 2022. Four seminars were held, with a focus on the Multi-Act project³⁷, on gender medicine, on AI, and on the Stall Catchers project³⁸.
- 2) Insights and presentations on Citizen Science have been offered to students attending:
 - the Master’s Degree in Biotechnology and Medical Biology, in 2022;
 - the Master’s in Science and Health Communication, in 2022 and 2023;
 - the course entitled “Open Science in practice: principles and tools for open access to scientific publications and research data”, offered to PhD students, in 2023;
 - the Master’s Degree in Nursing and Midwifery.
 - On the occasion of the mentoring visit hosted in May 2023, targeted initiatives were organised to raise awareness among researchers, professors, and research supporting offices.

Intervention Area “Support Resources & Infrastructures”

UniSR has hardly any resources and infrastructures for Citizen Science established yet and this has not changed since the stock-taking at the beginning of the project. The university does not offer any funding for Citizen Science projects and initiatives. However, it should be stated that the lack of significant institutional funding for research projects is not limited to Citizen Science. Since 2022 the core team of TIME4CS in UniSR acts as a contact point for Citizen Science within the organisation, using an ad-hoc email address (citizenscience@univr.it).

The UniSR core team working on the project has increased in the last year. Currently, there are different participants providing their expertise (e.g. research policy and integrity, science communication, public engagement, impact assessment, European policies, Open Science). The core team actively contributes to the project activities and to the implementation of GAs, providing their expertise for specific actions, such as the definition of relevant materials for the internal repository and the definition of communication measures (e.g. seminars).

³⁷ <https://www.multiact.eu/>

³⁸ <https://stallcatchers.com/main>

Intervention Area “Policy & Assessment”

The aim of supporting open science, science communication and public engagement is integrated in institutional research strategies and policies.

Concerning researchers’ evaluation schemes, science communication and public engagement are considered. Very soon the active involvement of citizens in research will be considered as well. Indeed, the revision of evaluation criteria for researchers, which have been developed as part of the TIME4CS Grounding Actions, is awaiting approval.

7.3. Overview of GAs, outputs and outcomes

In the previous section we have introduced the main institutional changes to support Citizen Science in UniSR. In this section we take a closer look at the Grounding Actions, their outcomes and impacts at the time of writing this deliverable.

Table 5: Evaluation model of UniSR

Grounding Actions	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
<p>1. Participation in a Citizen Science network</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Survey to better understand researcher awareness and understanding regarding Citizen Science ● Communication of activities related to Citizen Science will be organised in a communication plan ● Joining ECSA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● UniSR Researchers 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Survey co-created and distributed to Citizen Science researchers ● 112 researchers participated in the survey ● ECSA membership. ● Active engagement in the ECSA working group on Citizen Science and Health, Citizen Science and Universities and Storytelling and other Arts WGs. <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased knowledge of researcher awareness and understanding of Citizen Science. ● New knowledge and ideas coming from ECSA and TIME4CS used for GA2, 3 and 4.
<p>2. Implement changes in the organisational structures and functions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Formalization of the Open Science Team. ● Creation of the informal group for Citizen Science. ● Starting the engagement of research support services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● Management ● UniSR research community 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Open Science team established. ● Creation of an informal core group working on TIME4CS and on Citizen Science. ● Two information activities for research support services. <p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Level of stability of the core team and its confidence in Citizen Science.

Grounding Actions	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Level of engagement of the research supporting services. ● Increased knowledge on Citizen Science amongst members of the core team. ● Awareness of research support services regarding Citizen Science. ● Definition of a workflow to support researchers in Citizen Science activities.
<p>3. Set up information initiatives for researchers and training programs for students</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Starting the design of training sessions for students. ● Planning of seminars started. ● Launch of the series of seminars “Science & Society”. ● Launch of communication activities about Citizen Science. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● UniSR researchers ● UniSR students 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A strategy for the selection of speakers for the seminars “Science and Society”. ● 4 of the seminars organised ● 26 + 45 + 50 + 28 participants in 4 seminars ● Content for training activities elaborated. ● Citizen science integrated in the course dedicated to “Open Science in practice: principles and tools for open access to scientific publications and research data” for PhD students. ● Citizen science integrated in the Masters’ in Science and Health Communication. ● Citizen science integrated in the course Master’s Degree in Nursing and Midwifery. ● PhD course: No. of. students participating (49). Master course: No. of. students participating (20). Master’s Degree in Nursing and Midwifery: No. of students (30). ● Newsletter “Bits of Citizen Science” for researchers (14 issues) ● About 2000 recipients receive the newsletter. ● Publication of 5 articles on the project website. ● A poster for the Conference Citizen Science for Health. ● Participation in the conference GenOA Week, with a presentation on Citizen Science in UniSR. ● A poster for the EARMA Conference Odense 2024 <p>Outcome:</p> <p>Feedback of participants on the two seminars shows that the majority of people attending the events are interested in the topics covered and found the events useful.</p> <p>Increased knowledge and awareness about Citizen Science amongst UniSR researchers and students.</p>
<p>4. Identify an institutional contact point for Citizen Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Creation of a folder, accessible to the core team, for collection of materials for building the knowledge base on Citizen Science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● UniSR researchers 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A Citizen Science page in the Intranet was created in 2023 and made accessible to all UniSR employees. ● Citizen science support & materials offered on the Intranet are disseminated to the UniSR research community.

Grounding Actions	Engaged actors	Indicators at the end of 2023
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Creation of a dedicated email address as contact ● Creation of a section dedicated to Citizen Science in the intranet & its updates 		
<p>5. Adopt evaluation criteria for researcher evaluation that consider Citizen Science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Definition of specific evaluation criteria for Citizen Science. ● Adoption of specific criteria for Citizen Science. ● Ad-hoc communication. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Core team ● Management 	<p>Output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Potential integration of the current criteria for researchers' evaluation was elaborated, to make Citizen Science assessed in the researchers' careers. ● Criteria are in the process of approval.

8. Main lessons learned about the implementation process and recommendations

The 3-monthly Mutual Learning Meetings (Implementer Forums and Implementer Journeys) of Implementers and Frontrunners and the Final Evaluation Workshops helped to collect some interesting lessons learned from the implementation process of Grounding Actions that can be a rich source of information for other RPOs.

If RPOs want to implement institutional changes to support Citizen Science within their organisations, then the following recommendations are given:

Establishment of Citizen Science core teams

- Start with establishing a core team for Citizen Science, getting people from different research support services (e.g., Communication Department, Training Department, Funding Offices, Research Strategy Departments etc.) together, ideally also integrating former researchers into this core team.
- Invite external speakers to a very well adapted Citizen Science training for members of the core team.
- Based on the first training, create a shared understanding of potential benefits of different types of Citizen Science and try to find out which type of Citizen Science would be the easiest to start with in the specific organisational context.
- Encourage core team members to get involved with the Citizen Science community (national and international), to build bridges and learn from others.
- Get management and first interested researchers involved regularly in the core team activities to have the opportunity to link to this process.

Careful Planning and step-wise approach

- Take time as a core team to carefully plan future activities in a co-creation process, think of what is a prerequisite for further activities to happen. Invite colleagues into this co-creation process, try to understand what different groups (e.g., students, researchers) know about Citizen Science and what are their fears that need to be addressed.
- See where you can bundle forces with other institutes or projects (e.g., within your country or on a European level)
- Start with small Citizen Science initiatives as an „add-on” to the core research and collect first hand-experiences.
- Try to cross-finance a Citizen Science contact point with experience in Citizen Science who can support interested researchers. Ideally this Citizen Science contact point is not associated with one single faculty but supports all researchers (e.g., as part of the library).

Provision of Citizen Science training

- Do not make training too general, but rather adapt it to the very specific context of the RPO with concrete hands-on activities, where researchers understand how their research can be amended by Citizen Science elements.
- Provide smaller bits of information with very practical examples, make hands-on exercises which might result in concrete projects.
- Invite role models to training and workshops (external experts of the same research topic with experience in Citizen Science), this is very attractive for attendees.
- Have regular meetings with external Front-Runners from the same research field.

Motivation of researchers

- Try to convey the message to researchers (with the help of researchers in the core team): What are their fears, what do they need and aim for, how can Citizen Science support their needs?
- Think of financial and non-financial rewards for researchers and citizens to participate; integrate Citizen Science in evaluation schemes of researchers.
- It's hard to get the PIs involved, if they do not understand the value of Citizen Science for their research. So, provide individual training and/or start with the PhD students, provide them with small grants to initiate a Citizen Science project. Provide seed funding for Citizen Science to the young researchers.
- Be open to find new actors to engage in the Citizen Science projects (e.g. nurses turned out to a very interesting interface to citizens)

And here are further lessons learned:

Understand the concerns of the important stakeholder groups

When implementing Grounding Actions that should drive institutional changes from bottom-up, it always requires to have an eye on the main concern of researchers: to acquire funding for their research, conduct good research and be able to publish their results in high-impact journals.

Also, for the management, receiving funding is a key concern next to an increased visibility and reputation of their organisations. We have learned that within the Implementer organisations Citizen Science activities are well perceived by the management, being an integral part of many funding calls (e.g., Horizon Europe). But we also can observe that financial support is still an issue when it comes to sustainably supporting Citizen Science within organisations.

Citizen Science perceived as being triggered from "top to down" from the management

Many scientists in the RPOs perceive Citizen Science as being pushed from funding-down and bottom-up - requires reaching out to different stakeholders in the organisation - from management, to support staff, researchers and students - addressing all of them with a specific message that considers their needs and challenges. For this communication and internal networking task, good internal communication tools are important, to communicate the new content to the different audiences.

It also requires understanding formal institutional procedures, when triggering change in institutional policy documents and guidelines. These procedures must be followed and can be agencies as an "on-top" activity

for research in an extremely competitive environment that requires "on-top" skills and knowledge that many researchers do not have. For them it is difficult to differentiate Citizen Science from science communication, and participatory research, etc. They require a better understanding of the value of Citizen Science for their research, as well as role models and good practice that they can refer to. Citizen science facilitators are an important way to support researchers and act as change managers in this context. Also, "Inspiring Sessions" that show good practice projects from related fields of research and allow for the connection with other researchers interested in Citizen Science are an important Grounding Action.

Networks

Being part of and active in Citizen Science networks was perceived as very supportive and rewarding for the people who should trigger Citizen Science within their organisations. Networks help to exchange ideas and experiences with more experienced Citizen Science experts and thus widen one's own knowledge and perspectives about the topic. To gain more ease in handling Citizen Science activities, it was highly recommended to start with Citizen Science by "only" being a partner in a larger project, where newcomers could learn through observation and get consultation in the public engagement process. By working together with Citizen Science experts, new teams could be forged together and the possibility to get in contact with Citizen Science "ambassadors" improved.

During the TIME4CS project, networks were established and Implementers with basic levels of knowledge and experience in Citizen Science were very well supported by Front-Runners. But also reaching out to wider networks, like becoming a member of the ECSA and their working groups was an important outcome of TIME4CS so far and is highly recommended to other RPOs interested in Citizen Science.

Citizen Science facilitator or contact point

Implementers stressed the importance of a Citizen Science facilitator, who could not only provide information and advice to interested researchers, but also promote the topic internally and towards the management. We learned that the huge issue regarding this Citizen Science facilitator is sustainable funding. As there is no internal funding for this facilitator at this early stage of involvement in Implementer organisations, the funding is acquired externally (e.g., by research grants). Another approach is to add Citizen Science as an extra agenda to existing support staff, like teams for Open Science, Science Communication, and Strategy and Funding.

Support of management and initial funding

As mentioned earlier, the early involvement of the management is key for the implementation of Grounding Actions. For all Implementers, the Mentoring visit was a key moment in the implementation process, as management was present at the meetings and understood the value of Citizen Science for their institutions. From this moment on, the implementation of Grounding Actions was much easier in all implementer organisations.

Concrete information on successful Citizen Science projects

Successful stories are helpful to illustrate the benefits of Citizen Science to researchers and support staff, who are less familiar with the concept. These stories provide inspiration for the creation of new projects and

help to understand how usual pitfalls of citizens' engagement could be avoided. The challenge in this regard is how to initiate these successful stories if there are no Citizen Science projects organised in RPOs yet. A solution suggested by the Implementers was to search for external experts who have already been successfully implementing Citizen Science activities in a related research topic and invite them to present at "Inspiring Sessions" for researchers.

9. Main lessons learned of Front-Runners

WP5 organised two working sessions with Front-Runners to collect their lessons learned from the project: one during the consortium meeting in Brussels in 2022, and one during the final consortium meeting in Enschede at the end of 2023.

The workshops revealed that Front-Runners benefited a lot from the TIME4CS project as a result of the mutual learning experience with Implementers and the most important ones can be summarised as follows:

- All three Front-Runners, UCL, AU and UZH, benefited from the work with intervention areas and Grounding Actions to structure their own activities and have a better way to present them. They realised that they were triggering manifold activities to increase the uptake of Citizen Science within their RPOs, but without having a real strategy.
- They realised that there are so many different types of RPOs – also with the more disciplinary ones joining the project – and implementing institutional changes needs to be specific for each institution for the adoption to happen. Thus, there are so many paths needed to affect the organisation and it was fascinating for them to see how ambitious the Implementers planned, executed, reflected, adapted their paths and Grounding Actions towards institutional change.
- Front-Runners learned of the very different challenges that Implementers have about their top-down approach of institutionalising Citizen Science in comparison to a bottom-up approach taken in UCL and AU. Hearing about the struggle of other institutions made UZH realise the privileged position they have, being so strongly supported by their management and having relatively easy access to funding.
- All Front-Runners learned that it is important to think about the institutional context and that this context influences how to talk about Citizen Science and its effect. Surprisingly, despite the different contexts most institutions face the same challenges with regard to e.g. missing funding and knowledge on Citizen Science, etc.
- The interaction with Implementers made Front-Runners end up with a better argumentation for Citizen Science and an understanding on how Citizen Science works in other fields. They realised how crucial training is at all levels but getting the right audiences to buy in and attend is a challenge.
- The importance of Citizen Science champions was becoming even more evident, more specifically having Citizen Science champions at different levels of the organisations.
- Very specific and concrete information about Citizen Science projects, how they worked and what they have achieved, is important to have success stories for researchers, management, and support staff.
- During one of the exercises organised at the TIME4CS General Assembly (13-14 December 2022), Front-Runners started to formalise their own new Grounding Actions using the WP2 Reflection Tool.

This work and the support of Implementers on the detailed elaboration of Grounding Actions was a very useful experience for them.

- Finally, they are highly interested in the TIME4CS training modules to be used in their own organisations.

10. Monitoring of project KPIs

Next to collecting data on institutional change processes in implementer organisations and analysing the implementation journeys, WP5 was engaged in an overall project monitoring. The project developed a set of KPIs that are listed in the Description of Work of the Grant Agreement. Monitoring these KPIs supported the adaptive management in WP7 and allowed keeping track of the overall project performance. The main KPIs are listed below together with a description of the status when writing this deliverable.

sOBJ1. to increase knowledge on the actions leading to Institutional Changes in RPOs necessary to promote Public Engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology through a complete and up-to-date picture built upon the identification, mapping, monitoring and analysis of ongoing practices.

Table 6: KPIs for Objective 1

Expected Results at the end of the project:	Current situation:
Analysis of at least 30 case studies of institutional adoption of Citizen Science and Open Science	Achieved: Analysis of 38 case studies of Institutional adoption of CS and Open Science (see https://zenodo.org/record/6402091#.Y5bqTLKZPPY for the main lessons learned)
1 peer review publication on the institutional adoption of Citizen Science and Open Science	to come until the end of the project.
1 online repository containing all knowledge generated by the project (TIME4CS best practices and lesson learnt)	https://www.TIME4CS.eu/resources and https://www.zenodo.org/communities/TIME4CS/?page=1&size=20

sOBJ2. to support TIME4CS RPOs in the implementation of actions leading to Institutional Changes through the continuous mutual learning and knowledge transfer programme and the continuous exchange of knowledge and best practices between the RPOs with more experience in Institutional Change to support Citizen Science and those RPOs with less experience in this field.

Table 7: KPIs for Objective 2

Expected Results at the end of the project:	Current situation:
At least 7 knowledge transfer and mutual learning	Achieved: 3 frontrunner workshops have been

activities organised	<p>organised for frontrunners and implementing organisations to meet and exchange in WP3</p> <p>8 co-creation workshops have been organised within the implementing organisations to extend the core team working on the Grounding Actions</p> <p>4 Implementer Forums were organised to stimulate the knowledge exchange between Implementers</p> <p>12 Implementer Journey Reviews have been organised to stimulate the knowledge transfer between Front-Runners and Implementers</p> <p>1 Train-the-Trainer Workshop has been organised to adapt training modules to the needs of Implementers</p> <p>4 Mentoring visits have been organised where Frontrunners and support partners (APRE, ESF) visited Implementers to support the implementation of Grounding Actions and provide training</p> <p>1 Sustainability of Institutional Roadmaps Workshop organised with Implementers, Front-Runners and support partners (APRE, ESF, ZSI)</p>
At least 8 members of the personnel of implementer institutions trained about necessary actions leading to Institutional Changes	<p>At least 8 members of implementing institutions participated in the three frontrunner workshops. The co-creation workshops had overall 86 participants (11 CRG, 24 KTU, 35 Tyndall, 16 UniSR), local workshops in 2023 another 45 participants (5 CRG, 9 KTU, 4 Tyndall, 27 UniSR).</p> <p>The 4 mentoring visits served as a training for around 80 people from implementing institutions (amongst those 7 representatives of the higher management, 25 heads of departments, 30 researchers and students, representatives of funding organisations, communication departments, training departments, strategy and funding departments etc.)</p>
16 actions leading to Institutional Changes implemented by TIME4CS Implementers	37 actions leading to Institutional Changes defined and planned by TIME4CS Implementers (see D2.1, D2.3 and D2.4)
1 TIME4CS statement on how to promote Public Engagement and Citizen Science in RPOs through Institutional Changes	TIME4CS statement published on Zenodo ³⁹

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/time4cs/?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

A set of indicators to assess Institutional Changes to promote public engagement in science and Citizen Science	Indicators were developed and used during the stock-taking exercise and also in the evaluation models of Implementers.
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sOBJ3. To build a dynamic and inclusive community through the engagement of the most relevant stakeholders in the field of Citizen Science from academia, industry, government and civil society to include input to the RPOs from different actors.

Table 8: KPIs for Objective 3

Expected Results at the end of the project:	Current situation:
At least 40 stakeholders representing industry, governments, research and society mobilised by TIME4CS Implementers	Achieved: The local workshops organised by Implementers in 2023 had 45 participants representing industry, funding organisations, research and society. 86 participants took part in the co-creation workshops. And we also reached out to other RPOs during the analysis of the 38 case studies in WP1.
At least 14 training activities organised to support TIME4CS Implementers and build TIME4CS community	In the first two years we have 15 training activities organised to support the TIME4CS Implementers, which are all described in more detail in the technical report and are the Mutual Learning Exercises, the Implementer Forums and the Implementer Journey Reviews. These were complemented with 9 training workshops ⁴⁰ during the mentoring visits in 2023.
At least 150 stakeholders engaged on Citizen Science Helix	Currently the Citizen Science Helix ⁴¹ profiles 249 organisations and 794 users

Expected Results:

sOBJ4. to increase the awareness of R&I actors of the need for a sustainable and flexible organisation of RPOs governance system to better respond to the evolving relationship between science and society.

Table 9: KPIs for Objective 5

Expected Results at the end of the project:	Current situation:
1 website collecting relevant information about the implementation of Institutional Change to promote Citizen Science	Achieved: https://www.TIME4CS.eu/ not only provides information on Institutional Change but also helps to collect it via the case studies repository of (WP1).

⁴⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/8083037>

⁴¹ <https://crowdhelix.com/helices/citizen-science>

Expected Results at the end of the project:	Current situation:
At least 4 members of the governance of TIME4CS Implementers attending the mutual learning and knowledge transfer activities	4 members of the governance level were involved in the co-creation workshops, more than 30 during the mentoring visits.

In addition to the above KPIs that relate to reaching the project objectives, TIME4CS defined a number of outreach indicators.

Table 10: Outreach KPIs

Outreach KPIs	/KPIs	Current situation
Website. An advanced website, providing information about the project's results, including a detailed list and overview of all good practices collected by the consortium. In addition, the website will publish project's news and will act as a communication channel for the stakeholders.	~10000 total visits, 12 newsletters sent, 250 newsletter signed members	Achieved: Website visits - 25,472 (est) - 6.4K in 2023 12 newsletters sent 271 newsletter signed members
Visual Identity. visual identity, comprising a logo, standard presentation, brochure and roll-up in line with the H2020 visual guidelines.	1500 Brochures distributed during external events	236 Brochures* *see KPIs adjustment in D6.2
Social Media Accounts. The project activity will be distributed on Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook	1000 total followers among social medias	1310 total followers among social medias
Media presence, provided by interviews, journalistic articles, a video news release, complemented by info-graphics and fact sheets.	10 journalistic articles / interviews	4 journalistic articles so far

Outreach KPIs	/KPIs	Current situation
External events such as fairs and conferences that provide opportunities for in-depth discussions and exchange of knowledge.	Participation in 5 external events	So far the consortium took part in 8 external events (5 conferences, 3 events organised by sister projects)
Clustering activities to support close cooperation and joint dissemination strategies with other EU projects tackling similar issues. Periodic bilateral exchange of news & results, joint presence in events.	Cooperation with 5 initiatives	Currently in touch with 12 other EU funded projects, and participate in the Community of Practice for Training Coordinators in EU projects as well as the SwafS Projects CoP (new name: ECS Collaboration Group)
Workshops, webinars, participation in fairs. In order to support the dissemination of the project, the consortium partners will attend and/or organise various events, workshops and training activities. All events will be announced on the project’s website and communicated via social media.	organisation of 4 workshops organisation of 10 webinars	7 workshops (see technical report), 10 webinars organised
Citizen Science Helix. A virtual ecosystem/community tailor made for the TIME4CS Consortium as a launching pad to consolidate their ideas, harvest expertise from the wider CHX Network, build collaborative partnerships and to continue to function as a Citizen Science focused online community	150 stakeholders engaged on the helix	249 organisations and 794 users

11. Conclusions

After three years of implementing institutional changes that support Citizen Science in RPOs, we see that the approach of defining roadmaps and choosing Grounding Actions related to core intervention areas brought forward considerable results across the four Implementers. We also learned that the mutual exchange with Front-Runners was key in the whole implementation process as well as a continuous reflection of how to adapt Grounding Actions to the given situation. This leaves us with one of the key questions: how can such an approach towards institutional change scale, especially when not embedded in a public funding programme, such as TIME4CS?

The lessons learned on drivers and barriers for implementing change in RPOs towards more public participation in research has led to a set of recommendations described in this document. We tried to formulate these recommendations considering that there might be no or very little budget available to drive this change in RPOs. Thus, we suggest starting to build core teams with actors who are already part of research support services and thus are already embedded in institutional structures, with available resources. These core teams can greatly benefit from dedicated training, which can build on existing resources (e.g. available on EU-citizen.science and provided by the ECSA), before reaching out to researchers in their own organisations.

We learned that careful planning is important when starting to define Grounding Actions and recommend a stock-taking exercise at the start of the change process to document the point of departure (see D5.4 Monitoring Toolkit for RFOs and RPOs⁴² to find the stock-taking template). In a co-creation process that involves key actors from the institution and builds on a thorough understanding for the given situation, potential drivers and barriers for Citizen Science, a first action plan should be created and first steps should be defined.

Learning from other RPOs who are in the same field of research and more experienced in Citizen Science can strongly support this internal change process. The mutual learning can take the form of role models, inspirational talks, best practice Citizen Science examples and practical suggestions on how to implement changes within RPOs. Again, we see an important role here for ECSA and the wider European Citizen Science community. As a European network they can support mutual exchange and learning from others, triggering the uptake of Citizen Science within European RPOs. A key element will be trainings that are specifically designed for different stakeholders within RPOs (e.g., management, support services, researchers) and that can be adapted to the very specific contexts and fields of research of RPOs. The European Citizen Science Academy (ECS Academy), which is currently being set up in the context of the ECS project, is catering for this need of RPOs and will hopefully play an important role in the capacity building on Citizen Science in Europe. Capacity building materials and resources created within TIME4CS will also be available through this resource, as they are now available on the EU-citizen.science platform.

We also learned that early training of young researchers in the Citizen Science approach is an important step to build a “new generation” of researchers who understand the value of cooperation with the public and

⁴² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10405577>

know how to set up collaborative research processes. Likewise, the ECS Academy can serve as a reference for finding appropriate resources and training.

Still, more funding is needed for RPOs to build sustainable organisational structures that support Citizen Science. Often, fundamental changes are required that need additional resources and a dedicated budget. With the current resources, RPOs are already struggling with implementing excellent research in a highly competitive environment. Citizen science projects and Citizen Science performing organisations require a longer-term perspective. We see this as a call for funding agencies, which is embedded in the wider European discourse on how policy making can support Citizen Science more substantially. In the current situation, we do not have answers to questions such as: how can we avoid that once established connections between researchers and citizens end after short-term projects? How can we reach a sustainable funding of institutional Citizen Science contact points that does not depend on funding of short-term research projects? How can these connections be sustained long-term and how can they continually support future research activities? Requests from the Citizen Science community in Europe towards policy makers, such as the definition of new metrics to recognise Citizen Science in RPOs and RFOs, more funding for Citizen Science activities and a commitment to open science practices or the recognition of citizen-generated data are all relevant building blocks in bringing science and society closer together.

